

D.5.1

Technical report on free-living and plant-parasitic nematodes and ants' biodiversity, identifying key bioindicator species and functionality in olive groves.

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Executive Summary

This report outlines the status of two primary groups of ecological soil indicators in olive groves: nematodes and ants. Nematodes are categorized into two main groups: i) plant-parasitic nematodes and ii) free-living nematodes, which include all nematodes that are not plant-parasitic. Plant-parasitic nematodes are studied in the soil from olive rhizosphere and olive roots (probable olive parasites). The project found an overall diversity of 101 species of free-living nematodes and 111 species belonging to 32 genera in plant-parasitic nematodes in the five countries studied (Spain, Portugal, Morocco, Italy, and Greece) and the three different management systems (Traditional, Organic and High-density). Some of this species and genus have been described for the first time by science. The most diverse genera were *Paratylenchus* (17 species), followed by *Xiphinema* (16 species) and *Helicotylenchus* (7 species). Nematodes harmful to olive trees include root-lesion species (*Pratylenchus* spp.), which comprise seven species: *P. crenatus*, *P. neglectus*, *Pratylenchus* sp. 1WB_2017, *Pratylenchus* sp. WB, *P. thornei*, *P. vovlasi*, and *P. pratensis*. However, the most pathogenic species affecting fruit trees- *P. vulnus* and *P. penetrans*- were not found. Root-knot nematodes (*Meloidogyne* spp.) consisted of four species: *M. hispanica*, *M. javanica*, *M. arenaria*, and *M. incognita*, with a prevalence of 15,4% across 8 out of 52 groves. Among these, *M. javanica* was the most pathogenic and had the highest reproduction factor. Soil nematode samples from Morocco, Spain, Greece and Portugal were also tested for the presence of specific biocontrol agents including, *Arthrobotrys dactyloides*, *A. oligospora*, *Gamsylella gephyropagum*, *Catenaria* sp., *Hirsutella rhossiliensis*, and *Purpureocillium lilacinum*. *Gamsylella gephyropagum* and *Catenaria* sp. were not detected infecting nematodes and the most prevalent biocontrol agent was *P. lilacinum*. Finally, the nematode-trapping fungi were the less prevalent in the soil nematode samples with *A. dactyloides* and *A. oligospora* in olive groves from Greece and Morocco. Results suggest that high density management reduced the prevalence of the *P. lilacinum*, while traditional and organic management showed similar results, at exception of Portugal, where high-density management showed the highest presence of this fungal species.

A total of 21 traditional, 18 organic, and 11 intensive olive groves across Europe and Morocco were examined to assess how different management systems affect ant abundance and genus diversity. The spread of ants within the fields varied depending on the management type used. Intensive olive groves showed consistently lower ant abundance and diversity across all countries. Additionally, some genera, such as *Cataglyphis* spp., clearly preferred traditional groves. However, the data did not reveal a distinct clustering pattern of species based on management system. These results support the view that olive groves function as complex agroecological systems where natural resources like ants are not directly affected by the farming intensity. Regarding the ecological roles of ant communities, several beneficial genera were identified, including *Aphaenogaster*, *Camponotus*, *Crematogaster*, *Formica*, *Plagiolepis*, *Tapinoma*, and *Tetramorium*.

In conclusion, the management practices employed can indeed impact the abundance and diversity of ant assemblages in olive groves, which in turn play crucial roles in ecosystem functioning. However, when it comes to nematode (both free-living and plant-parasitic) abundance and biodiversity, the influence of field management appears to be more country-

specific. Organic and traditional practices also appear to be associated with higher levels of biocontrol activity against nematodes. Nevertheless, it is important to note that low biocontrol presence is still prevalent in many countries and conditions, indicating the need for improved soil biocontrol activity through the implementation of specific practices that promote microbial activity in the soil, such as increasing organic matter or reducing tilling.

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1. Introduction

1.1. Summary and scope

This report D5.1 aims to detail the composition of free-living and plant-parasitic nematodes and ant assemblages in selected olive groves with various management systems within the Soil O-live project. It seeks to offer diagnostic insights into the taxonomic diversity of these groups, highlighting their roles in essential soil functions such as pathogen control and nutrient cycling in olive groves. This data will support the development of effective soil amendments and restoration strategies.

1.2. Brief introduction on free-living and plant-parasitic nematodes

Soil nematodes are the most abundant metazoans in the planet (van den Hoogen et al., 2019; Orgiazzi et al., 2015). They are originally aquatic animals and are possible to find in all Earth ecosystems (including Antarctica). They are represented in most trophic levels of the soil food web involved in fundamental ecological processes (**Table 1**), such as nutrient cycling and movement of microorganisms from different soil layers and depth (Ferris, 2010). They respond in quantity and community structure to soil management and perturbation and for this reason, they can also be used as optimal biological indicators of perturbation of ecosystems (Bongers and Ferris, 1999). Several approaches have been developed for the biological monitoring of soil quality based on the abundance and structure of nematode assemblages (Sieriebriennikov et al., 2014). Biomonitoring using nematode taxa is built upon a classification based on life-cycle characteristics, in which soil nematodes are distributed among five classes along a colonizer-persister scale, or c-p, series (Sieriebriennikov et al., 2014). The range starts with nematodes in c-p-1, which are regarded as “enrichment opportunists”, being able to complete their life cycle in some cases in as short as two days, and their population sizes responding rapidly to pulses of nutrient input, being dominant in disturbed environments. In the contrary, c-p-5 nematodes may be considered “extreme persisters” that are generally intolerant to disturbance and inhabit stable, mature ecosystems with long life cycles (some of them for several months). Several indices have been calculated to monitor the degree of maturity of an ecosystem (i. e. Maturity Index, MI), or more related to plant-parasitic nematodes (i.e. Plant Parasitic Index, PPI) (Bongers et al., 1990; Bongers and Ferris, 1999). They could also be classified in several feeding groups (highly related with the structure of the buccal cavity): (i) Herbivores, feeding on living tissues of higher plants; (ii) carnivores feeding on animal tissues, vertebrates (as parasites) or invertebrate (as predators or parasites); (iii) fungivores feeding on fungi; (iv) bacterivores feeding on prokaryotic organisms; and (v) unicellular eukaryote feeders, feeding on ciliates, other protozoans or diatoms and unicellular algae. However, two major groups for functional analysis could be established, (i) plant-parasitic or herbivores and (ii) free-living nematodes (the rest of the nematode community). *This scheme has been followed in the tasks division in this project as plant-parasitic nematodes and the rest of nematodes as “free-living”.* Weighted proportions of functional guilds are used to infer various attributes of the food web and give rise to an Enrichment Index (EI) and a Structure

Index (SI). These indexes are correlated respectively with the intensity of nutrient enrichment and the degree of ecosystem maturity. Other index is the Channel Index (CI), calculated from the weighted proportions of fungivores of c-p-2 and bacterivores of c-p-1 and is considered to indicate whether the “fast” bacterial channel or “slow” fungal channel of energy transformation prevails in an ecosystem (Ferris et al., 2001; Ferris and Matute, 2003). These indexes, briefly explained, and others, such as diversity metrics describing alpha, beta and gamma diversity could explain the ecosystem quality of an ecological system, such as olive groves (Archidona-Yuste et al. 2020). However, we need to remain that olive and oil production is an economic activity and some alteration to the soil and the ecosystem will be produced, but measures should be introduced to reduce the impact to the minimal and maintaining the profitability and the viability of the farms.

Table 1. Some functions of nematodes in the soil food web (Ferris, 2010)

Channeling resources derived through herbivory
Channeling resources derived through bacterial and fungal decomposition
Accelerating turnover rates of decomposers
Priming beneficial functions and services of the food web
Regulating opportunists through predation
Regulating arthropod populations with soil life-stages
Serving as prey for higher level predators
Biodegradation of toxins
Influencing plant community composition and succession
Redistributing organisms in the soil matrix
Transporting organisms to new resources
Altering substrates to provide access to other organisms
Sequestering and redistributing minerals, carbon and energy

Recent studies indicated that the global diversity of plant-parasitic nematodes associated with the olive rhizosphere is estimated at about 250 species (Archidona-Yuste et al., 2019), many of them could live on weeds and feeding spontaneously on olive roots. However, unbalanced feeding groups (or specific plant-parasitic nematode species) in nematode communities in agroecosystems could limit the crop production and cause severe damage to plants. Specifically, in the case of olive production, important challenges have occurred in the last years involving the intensification of the crop by the use of synthetic fertilizers, irrigation, high density plantation, and the use in some areas of good land for the high-density groves, which involved good conditions (“conducive soil to the disease), such as continuous available water, high N levels and other nutrients in roots, abundance of roots and more concentrated in the soil wet bulb caused by drip irrigation. This has led to the damaging levels of some nematodes, such as the root-knot nematodes (*Meloidogyne* spp.), root-lesion nematodes (*Pratylenchus* spp.) or cyst-nematodes (*Heterodera mediterranea*), which could reduce the plant-growth and productivity levels of the groves. In this sense, the Spanish-CSIC nematological group has described several new species of *Meloidogyne* (*M. baetica* and *M. oleae*) (Castillo et al., 2003; Archidona-Yuste et al., 2018) and *Pratylenchus* (*P. oleae*) (Palomares-Rius et al., 2014) that infects olive trees. This could be a latent problem for new climatic conditions, new land and affect genetic resources for olive crop management. Other plant-parasitic nematodes could affect olive, but their areas are

more restricted than the ones mentioned before or their pathogenicity are not clearly studied (*Rotylenchulus* spp., *Paratylenchus* spp., *Xiphinema* spp., or *Helicotylenchus* spp.). Symptomatology of plants infected by plant-parasitic nematodes are usually in patches and associated with an unspecific symptomatology, and usually are associated with other agronomical problems (water deficiency, patches of low fertility or incorrect distribution of fertilizers...) and for the correct problem identification it is necessary a nematological soil and root analysis and diagnostic. Plant-parasitic nematode damage is related to the soil and nematode root density of the specific species and their damage is influenced by the nematode species, age of the plant, genotype, and environmental conditions. In this sense, young plantations in the presence of the high initial inoculum levels are more sensible than older and mature trees with an extensive root system exploring different soil layers.

Currently, in many European countries, any nematicide are authorized in the olive crop. However, some plant resistances have been found for some species of nematodes in some olive cultivars (Sasanelli et al., 2009). Spanish cultivars are susceptible to root-knot nematodes, but with different levels of reproduction which could help to choose cultivars that reproduce to a lesser extent the pathogen (Palomares-Rius et al. 2019). *Olea europaea* subsp. *cerasiformis* (genotype W147) and some accessions of wild olive *O. europaea* subsp. *sylvestris* (genotype W224 and DA 12I) have showed resistance to root-knot nematodes (Palomares-Rius et al., 2019; Sasanelli et al., 2009) and they could be use in future breeding programs and as rootstock (wild olive). Good sanitary, for example, plantlets free of plant-parasitic nematodes and removal of soil adhered to machinery could prevent the introduction of plant-parasitic nematodes to our field. Practices that promote soil health by reducing soil alteration and increasing organic matter levels in soil could promote the soil health and also a buffering effect with plant-parasitic nematode population levels that not cause damage to olive trees.

Plant-parasitic and free-living nematode levels could be regulated by the presence of biocontrol agents in the soil. Several reviews have showed the presence of a plethora of biocontrol agents, including fungi and bacteria, that could regulate nematode levels and the plant-parasitic nematofauna performance depending of the soil microbiota and directly by parasitism (Topalović et al., 2020; Pires et al., 2022). In this sense, the knowledge of how these microorganisms interact with the nematode populations and how different agronomical practices or agrochemicals in the soil interacts with them are of vital importance to design good practices to diversify and promote them in order to act as buffering control for plant-parasitic nematodes in the field. Just a few researches have studied the role of these biocontrol agents in the field from different approaches, such as the quantification of specific biocontrol agents in the nematode community by quantitative PCR in Spain olive groves (Campos-Herrera et al., 2022) and bioassay method using second-stage infective juveniles (J2) of root-knot nematodes in soil from olive nurseries in Morocco (Hamza et al., 2017a). However, the diversity and the activity levels of these biocontrol agents in olive fields in a broad scale in Europe and their relation to the cultural practices of the crop have not been studied. This project tries to understand these interactions, in order to select the most suitable practices to have a balanced ecosystem.

As each group needs specialized taxonomists the project has three specialized groups of taxonomists: i) free-living nematodes (UJA and CNR) (Task 5.1) and ii) plant-parasitic

nematodes (IAS-CSIC and CNR) (Task 5.2). Additionally, the number of nematodes in each sample has been determined by the IAS-CSIC and CNR posteriorly to the sample extraction.

Figure 1. Soil nematode sample after centrifugal-flotation method. See the different nematode species and sizes associated with other components of the soil, such as roots, decomposing organic matter and other soil fauna (10x magnification).

1.3. Brief introduction on ant assemblages

Among other groups of ground dwelling arthropods, ants belonging to family Formicidae, are a common biodiversity element of the Mediterranean olive groves. To date, approximately 12500 species of ants have been described and ant-specialised biologists estimate that the Formicidae family could include no less than twenty thousand species (Hölldobler and Wilson, 1990). Although ant species make up 2% of the known global insect fauna, they compose at least one-third of its biomass. For that reason, ants have been widely used to assess the impacts of soil management practices (Cotes et al., 2010), being considered as a key group because of their huge biomass.

The 12500 species described are distributed within 307 genera and 21 subfamilies, with most of them being geographically limited to tropical or subtropical regions. The *Myrmicinae* subfamily is by far the most diverse, since almost half of all ant species belong to this subfamily, with over 6000 described species within 144 genera. *Formicinae* comprises approximately 3000 species and *Ponerinae* includes a little more than 1100 species. Ultimately, *Dolichoderinae* subfamily represents the fourth most diverse subfamily of ants with approximately 700 species described. Many *Dolichoderinae* species have an arboreal lifestyle (*Dolichoderus*, *Tapinoma* or *Technomyrmex*), sometimes forming strong mutualistic associations with plants.

Additionally, ants are especially notable among the insects for their ecological dominance as predators, scavengers, and indirect herbivores. The most notorious group of herbivorous ants is found within the attine ant species (subfamily *Myrmicinae*, tribe *Attini*, subtribe *Attina*), which are also known as fungus-growing ants or leaf cutting ants. Another example of herbivory is pollinivory that has been discovered within the Neotropical ant genus *Cephalotes* and a few West Palaearctic species of the genera *Formica*, *Lasius* and *Myrmica* (Czechowski et al., 2011). One of the most widespread examples of plant material use is found among seed-harvesting and seed dispersing ants. Seed harvesting is especially common within the *Myrmicinae* genera specifically *Messor*, *Pogonomyrmex* as well as in some species of *Pheidole* found in arid habitats. This mutualistic interaction between ants and plants has been documented for approximately 11000 species of plants and is geographically widespread. Additionally, numerous ant species collect plant secretions directly from nectaries or indirectly from Hemipteran honeydew, creating a continuum of mutualism–exploitative ecological interactions.

Functionality of ant genera in the agroecosystem

Ants can also be predators, playing an important regulatory role on many arthropod populations and were among the first known examples of insects for biological control (Dinis 2014). Although some army ant species are specialised predators of other social insect societies, others are voracious generalist predators capturing all invertebrates and sometimes vertebrate preys that fail to escape, overwhelming their preys by their abundance. Some of the ant species have been referred as important for the suppression of the olive fruit fly, especially in its pupal stage. In fact, ants as generalist predators can be more efficient in biological control of pests than specialist natural enemies (Stiling and Cornelissen, 2005). Additionally, in a list of Dinis et al. (2016) on invertebrates that may feed on the pupae of the olive fruit fly it was found that the main predators were mainly composed by Formicidae. More specifically, species from the genera *Aphaenogaster*, *Camponotus*, *Cardiocondyla*, *Crematogaster*, *Formica*, *Lasius*, *Plagiolepis*, *Tapinoma* and *Tetramorium* are confirmed predators of the olive fly pupae, in the olive groves.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Participating olive groves

A total of fifty-one olive groves were monitored around the Mediterranean in Spain, Italy, Morocco, Greece, and Portugal, of which 21 belong to a traditional, 11 to a high-density, and 20 in Organic management systems (**Table 2**). Traditional cultivation encompasses different planting densities (between 5 and 12 meters spacing among trees) and can have 1 to 3 tree trunks. High-density olive groves include mostly mechanized cultivation with tree densities exceeding two hundred trees per hectare, and super intensive cultivation surpassing 1000 trees per hectare. Both traditional and high-density cultivation systems involve excessive soil tillage with heavy machinery, as well as the systemic application of herbicides and pesticides. Organic olive groves are based on the premise of total soil conservation and the preservation of biological resources without the use of chemical products.

Table 2. List of selected olive groves by countries and management systems (n = 52 fields)

SPAIN		
Traditional	High density	Organic
ES-TD1	ES-HD2	ES-ORG4
ES-TD5	ES-HD3	ES-ORG6
ES-TD7	ES-HD8	ES-ORG11
ES-TD9	ES-HD22	ES-ORG12
ES-TD15	ES-HD40	ES-ORG13
		ES-ORG14
MOROCCO		
Traditional	High density	Organic
MR-TD24	MR-HD25	MR-ORG23
MR-TD26	MR-HD28	
MR-TD27		
MR-TD29		
GREECE		
Traditional	High density	Organic
GR-TD30	GR-HD43	GR-ORG32
GR-TD31		GR-ORG33
GR-TD35		GR-ORG34
GR-TD36		GR-ORG38
GR-TD37		GR-ORG39
GR-TD46		GR-ORG45
GR-TD44		GR-ORG47
PORTUGAL		
Traditional	High density	Organic
PT-TD41	PT-HD51	PT-TD42
	PT-HD52	
	PT-HD53	
ITALY		
Traditional	High density	Organic
IT-TD16		IT-ORG17
IT-TD20		IT-ORG18
IT-TD21		IT-ORG19
IT-TD50		IT-ORG48
		IT-ORG49

2.2 Sampling procedure

An ecological evaluation is usually an essential component of any site management program, as this identifies, or confirms the features of interest, that are present and assesses their overall importance. This assessment forms the basis for setting the overall objectives for the site and conservation objectives for each feature, which can be considered one of the most important functions of the management planning process.

2.2.1 Free-living and plant-parasitic nematodes sampling procedure

The referred olive groves were sampled for soil and olive roots in the olive tree rhizosphere and procedure protocol with images was distributed among participants in WP5. Briefly, selected spot in the field (if irrigation is available, in the humid soil area where more active roots could be present) and the upper layer of soil debris was removed (with leaves and other organic matter), a subsample includes soil and active olive roots from 5 to 30 cm depth and at least 3 subsamples from nearby trees were mixed to compose a sample. From this sample 500 cm³ of soil and active secondary roots (at least 5 g) were included in the sample. 6 samples were asked to the project participants per field. Soil and roots were put into polythene bags, properly labeled and brought to the laboratory of Nematology, IAS-CSIC, and kept at 4 °C until processing. Afterward, nematode specimens were isolated from a 500 cm³ soil sub-sample using the centrifugal-flotation method (Coolen, 1979). The soil adhering to the root samples was gently removed, and the roots were observed for root-knot nematode infection (presence or absence of galls). Roots were weighed and blended in water and nematodes extracted following the protocol of Coolen (1979). In case of galls from root-knot nematodes were detected in feeder roots, the roots were blended in a 0.5% NaOCl solution for 4 min and followed the protocol described in Hussey and Barker (1973). Soil nematodes were shared from the same extraction between IAS-CSIC (Task 5.2, plant-parasitic nematodes) and UJA (Task 5.1, free-living nematodes). Soil and root nematodes were identified under stereomicroscope and kept in DESS (a solution for nematode morphology preservation and DNA) (Yoder et al., 2006). IAS-CSIC performed an Integrative Taxonomy (combination of morphology-morphometry with molecular markers for nematode identification) in the majority of the samples and the molecular markers were obtained from the same PCR tube coming from single individual without any exception. For molecular analyses, DNA of one nematode was extracted individually in order to avoid species mixture in the sample was conducted as described by Castillo et al. (2003). Depending of the genus, several markers were studied (ribosomal or mitochondrial genes) and different primers were used (Castillo et al., 2003). In some cases, such as root-knot nematodes (*Meloidogyne* spp.), since *M. arenaria*, *M. incognita* and *M. javanica* are the most predominant RKN species in Spain, molecular identification of *Meloidogyne* was performed using a multiplex PCR assay (Kiewnick et al., 2013). In case of negative results with these species, the region of the mitochondrial genome between the cytochrome oxidase subunit II (coxII) and 16S rRNA mitochondrial DNA (mtDNA) genes was amplified and sequenced using primers C2F3 (5'-GGTCAATGTTTCAGAAATTTGTGG-3') (Powers and Harris, 1993) and MRH106 (5'-AATTTCTAAAGACTTTTCTTAGT-3') (Stanton et al., 1997). The reference *M. arenaria*, *M. incognita* and *M. javanica* populations from olive trees previously identified and maintained on tomatoes in the greenhouse served as a positive control throughout this study. UJA team fixed the nematodes in formaldehyde (4%), mounted the nematode on slides and identified each nematode in each soil sample.

Table 3. Olive groves, country, management system and number of nematode samples extracted from soil (500 cm³) and roots. Samples were extracted by IAS-CSIC team and shared with UJA (plant-parasitic nematodes studied by IAS-CSIC and free-living nematode studied by UJA). Italian samples were extracted and analyzed by CNR because of *Xylella fastidiosa* risk from Italy.

Orchard name	Country	Cultivation method	N° sampled extracted IAS-CSIC		N° samples analyzed		
					IAS-CSIC	CNR	UJA
			Soil	Roots ^a			

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ES-TD1	Spain	Traditional	6	6	6/6	-	6
ES-TD5	Spain	Traditional	6	6	6/6	-	6
ES-TD7	Spain	Traditional	6	6	6/6	-	6
ES-TD9	Spain	Traditional	6	6	6/6	-	0
ES-TD15	Spain	Traditional	6	6	6/6	-	0
ES-ORG4	Spain	Organic	6	6	6/6	-	6
ES-ORG6	Spain	Organic	6	6	6/6	-	6
ES-ORG11	Spain	Organic	6	6	6/6	-	0
ES-ORG12	Spain	Organic	6	6	6/6	-	0
ES-ORG13	Spain	Organic	6	6	6/6	-	0
ES-ORG14	Spain	Organic	6	6	6/6	-	0
ES-HD2	Spain	High Density	6	6	6/6	-	6
ES-HD3	Spain	High Density	6	6	6/6	-	6
ES-HD8	Spain	High Density	6	6	6/6	-	6
ES-HD22	Spain	High Density	6	6	6/6	-	0
ES-HD40	Spain	High Density	6	6	6/6	-	0
PT-TD41	Portugal	Traditional	6	6	6/6	-	2
PT-ORG42	Portugal	Organic	6	6	6/6	-	2
PT-HD51	Portugal	High Density	6	6	6/6	-	0
PT-HD52	Portugal	High Density	6	6	6/6	-	2
PT-HD53	Portugal	High Density	6	6	6/6	-	0
MR-TD24	Morocco	Traditional	6	-	6/0	-	2
MR-TD26	Morocco	Traditional	6	-	6/0	-	0
MR-TD27	Morocco	Traditional	6	-	6/0	-	0
MR-TD29	Morocco	Traditional	6	-	6/0	-	0
MR-ORG23	Morocco	Organic	6	-	6/0	-	2
MR-HD25	Morocco	High Density	6	-	6/0	-	2
MR-HD28	Morocco	High Density	6	-	6/0	-	0
GR-TD30	Greece	Traditional	6	6	6/6	-	0
GR-TD31	Greece	Traditional	6	6	6/6	-	0
GR-TD35	Greece	Traditional	6	6	6/6	-	2
GR-TD36	Greece	Traditional	6	6	6/6	-	0
GR-TD37	Greece	Traditional	6	6	6/6	-	0
GR-TD44	Greece	Traditional	6	6	6/6	-	0
GR-TD46	Greece	Traditional	6	6	6/6	-	0
GR-ORG32	Greece	Organic	6	6	6/6	-	2
GR-ORG33	Greece	Organic	6	6	6/6	-	0
GR-ORG34	Greece	Organic	6	6	6/6	-	0
GR-ORG38	Greece	Organic	6	6	6/6	-	0
GR-ORG39	Greece	Organic	6	6	6/6	-	0
GR-ORG45	Greece	Organic	6	6	6/6	-	0
GR-ORG47	Greece	Organic	6	6	6/6	-	0
GR-HD43	Greece	High Density	6	6	6/6	-	2
IT_TD16	Italy	Traditional	-	-	0	3/0 ^b	0
IT_TD20	Italy	Traditional	-	-	0	3/0 ^b	0
IT_TD21	Italy	Traditional	-	-	0	6/0	0
IT_TD50	Italy	Traditional	-	-	0	3/0 ^b	0
IT_ORG17	Italy	Organic	-	-	0	3/0 ^b	0
IT_ORG18	Italy	Organic	-	-	0	3/0 ^b	0
IT_ORG19	Italy	Organic	-	-	0	3/0 ^b	0
IT_ORG48	Italy	Organic	-	-	0	6/0	0
IT_ORG49	Italy	Organic	-	-	0	6/0	0

^a: no roots were found in sample bag from Morocco and Italy.

^b: Only 3 samples were submitted from these fields.

Nematode biocontrol agents (5.2 Task performed by IAS-CSIC).

Several methods were used to identify the biocontrol agents infecting nematodes in the soil. A few grams of soil from groves were dried at room temperature and kept a 4 °C until use. Plate culturing were not chosen because of the noise with other microorganisms and we selected methods straighter related to the activity of biocontrol agents in nematode community. 3 out of the 6 soil samples from each field were studied in order to reduce the number of samples, giving a significant and robust amount of information. The selection of the samples was done with pair number (2, 4 and 6). Two assays were chosen:

- i) *qPCR of a selection of different biocontrol agents with different mode of action in the nematode community (Table 4)*: Many biocontrol agents could be detected in the rhizospheric soil, but living as endophytes inside the roots or in the soil organic matter, and in this way, we are not sure about their role in the soil food web consuming nematodes. The detection of active biocontrol agents against nematodes in the extracted nematodes from the soil could give us the reality of biocontrol agents acting against nematodes and eggs. This procedure has been used in a former study in the IAS-CSIC (Campos-Herrera et al., 2022). Briefly, the nematode sample kept in DESS and after nematode identification was diluted and filtered for nematode concentration and DESS removal. Total sample nematode was extracted using DNA extraction kit PowerSoil® DNA Isolation Kit (MOBIO Laboratories, Inc, Carlsbad, CA, USA). DNA samples were analyzed for quality and quantity using a Qubit 4 Fluorometer (Thermo Fisher Scientific Inc., Waltham, MA, USA) and stored at - 30 °C until qPCR analysis. A total of 6 nematophagous fungi with different way of nematode parasitism were screened: nematode-trapping (*Arthrobotrys dactyloides*, *A. oligospora* and *Gamsyella gephyropagum*), endoparasitic (*Catenaria* sp. and *Hirsutella rhossiliensis*) and eggs-parasitic fungi (*Purpureocillium lilacinum*). The qPCR assays were performed with species-specific primers and Taqman probes. All real-time qPCR assays were performed on an CFX Connect Real Time PCR System (Bio-Rad Laboratories, Inc.) in hard-shell PCR plates 96-well, thin well (Bio-Rad Laboratories, Inc.). These target organisms were detected in independent runs with negative (no sample) controls in all plates, with two technical repetitions per sample. Reactions were performed in a final volume of 20 µL and contained 1x iTaq Universal Probes Supermix (Bio-Rad Laboratories, Inc.), 300 nM BSA (New England BioLabs, Inc.) and 2 ng of DNA per reaction. The specific primers and probes used in this study are shown in **Table 4**. Primers and probes concentrations as well as qPCR conditions were as described by Atkins et al. (2005), Zhang et al. (2006) and Pathak et al. (2012) (**Table 4**).
- ii) *Egg-bait bioassay in agar-water*: dry soil from the same samples from qPCR were distributed on Petri dishes (9-cm diameter) containing a growth restricting medium (streptomycin, 50 mg l⁻¹; chloramphenicol, 50 mg l⁻¹; chlortetracycline, 50 mg l⁻¹; Rose Bengal, 50 mg l⁻¹; triton, 1 ml l⁻¹; and 1% agar) (Lopez-Llorca and Duncan, 1986) and 500 eggs were distributed between the two soil rows (**Fig. 2**). Plates were incubated at 25 ± 0.5°C for twelve days. Number of parasitized eggs was recorded after twelve days under a dissecting microscope and percentage of parasitism was then calculated as the number of parasitized eggs/total number of eggs counted (around 100 eggs per plate) per plate. Eggs were considered

parasitized if fungal hyphae grew from inside. Parasitized eggs were individually transferred to potato dextrose agar (PDA) to establish pure cultures of the fungi. ITS identification of fungal species isolated was carried out by PCR amplification and sequencing of the internal transcribed spacers (ITSs) of the rDNA regions. DNA was extracted from 50 mg of mycelium collected from cultures on PDA using the i-genomic Plant DNA Extraction Mini kit (iNtRON biotechnology, Seongnam, South Korea) according to the protocol described by the manufacturer. The PCR reaction was performed in 25 μ l mix that contained 1 μ l of the DNA extraction, 10.5 μ l MiliQ water (Qiagen), 12.5 μ l Taq PCR Master Mix (Qiagen) and 0.5 μ l of each primer (5 pmol), PCR conditions were the same as those described in the original studies (White et al., 1990) with primers ITS1F (Gardes and Bruns, 1993) and ITS4 (White et al., 1990). PCR products were cleaned using MinElute PCR Purification Kit (Qiagen) and sequenced by Stabvida (Caparica, Portugal). DNA sequences were analyzed using the BLAST database and assigned to the reference isolate sequences with the highest bit score.

Table 4. Fungal biocontrol agents tested in the nematode extraction from each field at IAS-CSIC. Different mode of action has been checked in order to find the functional role of this biocontrol agents in the soil nematode community.

Organism	Sequence primers and probe (5'-3')	References	MODE OF ACTION
<i>Arthrobotrys dactyloides</i>	F: AGGTCGGTTTTGAGCTGGCTTA	Pathak et al., 2012; Campos-Herrera et al., 2019	NEMATODE-TRAPPING FUNGI
	R: CCACCCACCTAGAACAAGTATGT		
	P: FAM-ACCCAAGCCGGTTTTAAAGT-MGB		
<i>A. oligospora</i>	F: CGGTTTGCTGTTGCAGCTTGTT	Pathak et al., 2012; Campos-Herrera et al., 2019	NEMATODE-TRAPPING FUNGI
	R: GGTTCAAAAGGGTTTACCAGG		
	P: FAM-CTGTCTTCCGGTTGGTAAGC-MGB		
<i>Gamsylella gephyropagum</i>	F: GTCGTAACAAGTTTTCCGTAGG	Pathak et al., 2012	NEMATODE-TRAPPING FUNGI
	R: TTGTAATGGGTGCCAGCG		
	P: FAM-CCAAAACATAGCTGTCCGGT-MGB		
<i>Catenaria sp.</i>	F: GCCGTGTAGGCAAAAATTCCGACT	Pathak et al., 2012; Campos-Herrera et al., 2019	ENDOPARASITES
	R: GCAGCCTGGATTGTTTGATGGCCT		
	P: FAM-TGCTCAACGTCACGAGTAAACCAACA-MGB		
<i>Hirsutella rhossiliensis</i>	F419: TGCAGTAGCTCCCAGAG	Zhang et al., 2006; Campos-Herrera et al., 2012	ENDOPARASITES
	R480: TTGTTTTACGGCGTGACCG		
	P442: FAM-TCGCACCGGAAACGCGGAG-TAMRA		
<i>Purpureocillium lilacinum</i>	PLrtF: GACCCAAAACCTTTTTGCATTACG	Atkins et al., 2005	EGGS-PARASITIC FUNGI
	PLrtR: AGATCCGTTGTTGAAAGTTTTGATTCATTGTTTTG		
	PLrt P: FAM-CCGCGGAATTTCTCTCTGAGTTGC-TAMRA		

Figure 2. Eggs from *M. incognita* used as bait for bioassay in water-agar using soil from different soils sampled in project Soil O-live.

2.2.2 Ant assemblages monitoring stations

In each of the referred olive groves, three monitoring stations per hectare were chosen for assessing the ant assemblages. The monitoring stations in this occasion are three due to the destructiveness of the method. A differentiation in sampling spots is important since some ant genera may be more easily detected in some habitats than in others. More specifically, the standard method chosen for the assessment of the ant assemblages was based on the general principles of randomized selection of sub-plots, as not to create a subjective bias. Each olive grove was divided into one hundred plots per hectare, where each of them had a size of ten square meters (10x10m). Using a Random Number Generator, 5 plots are selected based on the 5 random numbers generated. The same process was followed within each of the 10x10m subplots, in order to select three smaller subplots where the pitfall traps would be placed (**Fig. 3**). The chosen stations were the same for the whole duration of the experiment, allowing repeated visits for re-sampling the ant assemblages in different weather conditions. Stations on site had to be at least 1m away from the trunk of the tree.

Figure 3. Orthophotograph of olive grove cropped from Google Earth of 1 hectare merged with a sub-plot Grid generated in Excel (100 equal-sized cells with numbering).

Figure 4. Establishing a pitfall using propylene–glycol in a buried plastic cup.

Each station is defined using a pitfall trap, a vertical-sided container that is dug into the ground so that the top is leveled with or below the ground surface; invertebrates walking along the ground inadvertently fall into the trap. Pitfall trapping is probably the most widely used method for sampling invertebrates and is a cheap and straightforward way of catching a large number of invertebrates (Santos et al., 2020). In most cases, Propylene-glycol odorless liquid is added. An example of the layout of a pitfall is illustrated in **Fig. 4**. The pitfall location was marked by pegs.

2.3 Assessing the free-living and plant-parasitic nematode biodiversity

Tasks 5.1 (free-living) and Task 5.2 (plant-parasitic nematodes and nematode biocontrol agents) will assess the biodiversity of nematodes based on the number of nematodes (total) and the number of each respective task counting. Adults are the main stage for nematode identification at genus level. In some genera, the juvenile stages could separate the species, but in some cases, the number of the identified adults will be related to the number of juveniles of the genera and will be associated to each species in the case of more than one species for the same genera (i. e. *Paratylenchus*). Some alpha diversity indices will be calculated to understand the diversity for each agricultural system (traditional, organic and high-density) and for each country (Spain, Portugal, Morocco, Italy and Greece). Only one sampling time was used for assessing nematode biodiversity. Spring is the best period of the year for this task. However, some parts of Europe during that year were suffering an extreme drought period (i.e. Andalusia).

2.3.1 Inventory of free-living and plant-parasitic nematodes

In the results section will be included the inventory of all nematodes found in Task 5.1 and Task 5.2. Additionally, to the tables presented in this report, the main idea is to publish the data in an open access journal and the molecular barcodes (ribosomal and mitochondrial sequences) for unequivocal species identification will be deposited in open access

repositories, such as GenBank (NCBI) once the data will be published.

2.4 Assessing ant biodiversity

For measuring the abundance of ant assemblages, we assessed the number of individuals present in each trap. Since each olive grove is stratified, data were expressed as number per sample unit (total number from all traps in one unit), in order to compare numbers from sample units from areas with different habitats.

Ant monitoring was conducted in each plot from late April to late May, with weekly sampling. To assess ant abundance in each olive grove, the focus was on the total number of ants captured throughout the month, summed across all monitoring stations. Results included data from the 2023 sampling campaign and representative olive groves

Inventory of ant assemblages

In all olive groves, ant individuals were collected and classified at genus or, more often at species level (**Fig. 5**) using taxonomical books and keys for ant fauna.

Figure 5. Samples of preserved biological material.

2.5 Data analyses

We analyze ant abundance, alpha and beta biodiversity using a Hill Number approach and Jaccard indices, respectively, by employing the Vegan package in R.

3. Results

NEMATODE SAMPLES

A total of 294 soil samples and 216 olive root samples for nematode extraction were

received at IAS-CSIC (258 soil samples and 216 olive root samples) and CNR (36 soil samples) for total nematode extraction and tested following the described method (see **Table 3**). 6 soil and root samples/field were asked to participants.

- **Morocco** – 42 soil samples from 7 groves have been received (100% from the expected soil samples and 0% of the expected root samples).
- **Spain** – 96 soil and root samples from 16 groves have been received (100 % from the expected soil and root samples).
- **Greece** – 90 soil and root samples from 15 groves have been received (100 % from the expected soil and root samples).
- **Portugal** – 30 soil and root samples from 5 groves have been received (100 % from the expected soil and root samples).
- **Italy** – 36 soil samples from 9 groves have been received (66.7 % from the expected soil samples and 0% of the expected root samples).

ANT SAMPLES

Only samples from Greece and Morocco were obtained and analyzed at this point for this report.

3.1 Free-living nematodes (Task 5.1, UJA, CNR)

At present, 178 soil samples have been examined, 96 collected in Spain, 22 in Greece, 18 in Morocco and 30 in Portugal, having a representation of three kinds of management (traditional, organic and high density) for the four countries. A total of 14680 nematodes belonging to 122 species of nine different orders were mounted on permanent glass slides and identified.

The richest nematode orders were Dorylaimida and Rhabditida, with 47 and 46 species, respectively.

The estimated abundance for free-living nematodes reached an overall average of 862 ± 616 (70 – 3890) specimens per 500 cm³ of soil. Nevertheless, values vary in the four countries, with a maximum (1107 ± 828 (340 – 3890)) in Morocco, intermediate (1037 ± 720 (100 – 2890)) in Greece, and minimum in the two Iberian countries, namely Spain (800 ± 470 (90 – 2210)) and Portugal (788 ± 748 (70 – 3730)) (**Fig. 6**).

Figure 6. Abundance of **free-living nematodes** per 500 cm³ of soil including different types of grove management

Species richness (= number of species per soil sample) was $14 \pm 5,3$ (2 – 36) in overall average, and displayed a distribution pattern to that observed for abundance. Actually, Greece presented the highest richness ($15,7 \pm 6,6$ (6 – 36)), followed of Spain (15 ± 5 (4 – 30)), Morocco ($14 \pm 3,7$ (7 – 21)) and Portugal ($9,7 \pm 3,7$ (2 – 18)) (**Fig. 7**). Regarding the effect of tillage method on nematode fauna, the results herein provided suggest that, in general, organic and traditional groves contain higher number of species and specimens than the intensive ones. Besides, Shannon diversity index shows a similar trend (**Fig. 8**).

Figure 7. Species richness of **free-living nematodes** per 500 cm³ of soil including different types of grove management.

Figure 8. Shannon index for **free-living nematodes** per 500 cm³ of soil including different types of grove management.

Nevertheless, the observed differences should be taken with caution as the soil samples studied in the four countries significantly differ between them. In Spain, the larger number of soil samples provides a more robust dataset, allowing for clearer and more reliable identification of patterns and trends. These well-founded trends are also observed in other countries, such as Greece, however, in those cases, they should be interpreted with caution due to the lower sampling effort or less thorough study of the samples.

Available results from Italian groves with two tillage methods (traditional and organic) show an average abundance of $63,67 \pm 34,18$ (26 – 178) nematodes per 100 cm³ of soil sample, belonging to 13 taxa, with $4,11 \pm 1,6$ (2 – 8) taxa per soil sample, and organic groves showing highest values than the traditional ones.

Table 5 presents the list of free-living taxa identified at the species level. Several of these taxa likely represent new species that will require more detailed description in future and inside the frame of this project. Spanish organic groves showed the highest diversity, with 77 taxa recorded, followed by Spanish high-density groves and Greek organic groves, each with 64 taxa. In contrast, some specific countries and management systems were poorly sampled, which may limit the interpretation of the results of these treatments.

Table 5. Free-living nematode species found in the rhizosphere of olive in five countries around the Mediterranean basin (Spain, Morocco, Portugal, Italy, and Greece) with different crop management (Traditional, Organic and high-density).

Spain	Traditional 62 taxon/30 samples	Organic 77 taxon/36 samples	High-density 64 taxon/30 samples
	<i>Acrobeles complexus</i>	<i>Achromadora</i> sp.	<i>Acrobeles complexus</i>
	<i>Acrobeles singulus</i>	<i>Acrobeles complexus</i>	<i>Acrobeles singulus</i>
	<i>Acrobeloides nanus</i>	<i>Acrobeles singulus</i>	<i>Acrobeloides nanus</i>
	<i>Acrobeloides tricornis</i>	<i>Acrobeloides nanus</i>	<i>Acrobeloides tricornis</i>
	<i>Acromoldavicus skrjabini</i>	<i>Acromoldavicus skrjabini</i>	<i>Aporcelaimellus hyalinus</i>
	<i>Alaimus</i> sp.	<i>Alaimus</i> sp.	<i>Aporcelaimellus obtusicaudatus</i>
	<i>Aporcelaimellus hyalinus</i>	<i>Aporcelaimellus hyalinus</i>	<i>Aporcelinus</i> sp.
	<i>Aporcelaimellus obtusicaudatus</i>	<i>Aporcelaimellus obtusicaudatus</i>	<i>Aporcella</i> sp. 1
	<i>Aporcella</i> sp. 1	<i>Aporcella</i> sp. 1	<i>Aporcella</i> sp. 3
	<i>Aulolaimus cribatus</i>	<i>Aporcella</i> sp. 2	<i>Aulolaimus cribatus</i>
	<i>Aulolaimus quercophilus</i>	<i>Aporcella</i> sp. 3	<i>Aulolaimus quercophilus</i>
	<i>Belondira tarjani</i>	<i>Aulolaimus cribatus</i>	<i>Belondira tarjani</i>
	<i>Bursilla vernalis</i>	<i>Aulolaimus quercophilus</i>	<i>Bursilla vernalis</i>
	<i>Campydora</i> sp.	<i>Belondira tarjani</i>	<i>Capitellus caramborum</i>
	<i>Capitellus caramborum</i>	<i>Bursilla vernalis</i>	<i>Cephalobus persegnis</i>
	<i>Cephalobus persegnis</i>	<i>Campydora</i> sp.	<i>Ceratoplectus armatus</i>
	<i>Ceratoplectus armatus</i>	<i>Capitellus caramborum</i>	<i>Cervidellus vexilliger</i>
	<i>Cervidellus vexilliger</i>	<i>Cephalobus persegnis</i>	<i>Chiloplacus bisexualis</i>
	<i>Chiloplacus bisexualis</i>	<i>Ceratoplectus armatus</i>	<i>Chiloplacus membranifer</i>
	<i>Chiloplacus minimus</i>	<i>Cervidellus vexilliger</i>	<i>Chiloplacus mysteriosus</i>
	<i>Chiloplacus mysteriosus</i>	<i>Chiloplacus bisexualis</i>	<i>Chiloplacus tenuis</i>
	<i>Chiloplacus tenuis</i>	<i>Chiloplacus membranifer</i>	<i>Chiloplacus trilineatus</i>

Deliverable 5.1

	<i>Chiloplacus trilineatus</i>	<i>Chiloplacus minimus</i>	<i>Clarkus papillatus</i>
	<i>Clarkus papillatus</i>	<i>Chiloplacus mysteriosus</i>	<i>Coomansus parvus</i>
	<i>Coomansus parvus</i>	<i>Chiloplacus tenuis</i>	<i>Crassolabium etterbergense</i>
	<i>Crassolabium etterbergense</i>	<i>Chiloplacus trilineatus</i>	<i>Diphtherophora</i> sp.
	<i>Diphtherophora</i> sp.	<i>Clarkus papillatus</i>	<i>Discolaimium</i> sp.
	<i>Discolaimium</i> sp.	<i>Coomansus parvus</i>	<i>Discolaimus major</i>
	<i>Dorylaimellus egmonti</i>	<i>Crassolabium etterbergense</i>	<i>Discolaimus mariae</i>
	<i>Dorylaimellus globatus</i>	<i>Diphtherophora</i> sp.	<i>Dorylaimellus egmonti</i>
	<i>Dorylaimellus grandis</i>	<i>Discolaimium</i> sp.	<i>Dorylaimellus globatus</i>
	<i>Dorylaimellus neocapitatus</i>	<i>Discolaimus major</i>	<i>Dorylaimellus grandis</i>
	<i>Drilocephalobus coomansi</i>	<i>Discolaimus mariae</i>	<i>Dorylaimellus neocapitatus</i>
	<i>Drilocephalobus moldavicus</i>	<i>Discolaimus</i> sp.	<i>Dorylaimellus parvulus</i>
	<i>Ecumenicus monohystera</i>	<i>Dorylaimellus egmonti</i>	<i>Dorylaimellus</i> sp. 1
	<i>Ereptonema articum</i>	<i>Dorylaimellus globatus</i>	<i>Drilocephalobus coomansi</i>
	<i>Eucephakobus mucronatus</i>	<i>Dorylaimellus grandis</i>	<i>Drilocephalobus goodeyi</i>
	<i>Eucephalobus striatus</i>	<i>Dorylaimellus parvulus</i>	<i>Drilocephalobus moldavicus</i>
	<i>Eudorylaimus</i> sp. 1	<i>Drilocephalobus coomansi</i>	<i>Ecumenicus monohystera</i>
	<i>Eudorylaimus</i> sp. 2	<i>Drilocephalobus moldavicus</i>	<i>Ereptonema articum</i>
	<i>Heterorhabditis</i> sp.	<i>Ereptonema articum</i>	<i>Eudorylaimus</i> sp. 1
	<i>Kochinema secutum</i>	<i>Eucephalobus mucronatus</i>	<i>Eudorylaimus</i> sp. 2
	<i>Mesodorylaimus ibericus</i>	<i>Eudorylaimus</i> sp. 1	<i>Heterorhabditis</i> sp.
	<i>Mesorhabditis minuta</i>	<i>Eudorylaimus</i> sp. 2	<i>Kochinema secutum</i>
	<i>Microdorylaimus</i> sp.	<i>Eudorylaimus</i> sp. 4	<i>Mesodorylaimus ibericus</i>
	<i>Mylonchulus brachyuris</i>	<i>Heterorhabditis</i> sp.	<i>Mesorhabditis minuta</i>
	<i>Oscheius tipulae</i>	<i>Kochinema secutum</i>	<i>Metaporcelaimus</i> sp.
	<i>Panagrolaimus rigidus</i>	<i>Margollus</i> sp.	<i>Metaxonchium</i> sp.
	<i>Paracephalobus bodenheimeri</i>	<i>Mesorhabditis minuta</i>	<i>Microdorylaimus</i> sp.
	<i>Paravulvus cf. teres</i>	<i>Metaxonchium</i> sp.	<i>Mylonchulus subsimilis</i>
	<i>Plectus parvus</i>	<i>Microdorylaimus</i> sp.	<i>Oleaxonchium olearum</i>
	<i>Prionchulus cf. punctatus</i>	<i>Mylonchulus subsimilis</i>	<i>Panagrolaimus cf. magnivulvatus</i>
	<i>Prismatolaimus</i> sp.	<i>Nygolaimus seguranus</i>	<i>Panagrolaimus rigidus</i>
	<i>Protorhabditis</i> sp.	<i>Odontolaimus</i> sp.	<i>Panagrolaimus superbus</i>
	<i>Pseudacrobeles (B.) pseudolatus</i>	<i>Oleaxonchium olearum</i>	<i>Paracephalobus bodenheimeri</i>
	<i>Pseudacrobeles (P.) unguicolis</i>	<i>Oscheius tipulae</i>	<i>Paravulvus cf. teres</i>
	<i>Tripyla</i> sp.	<i>Oxydirus oxicephalus</i>	<i>Plectus parvus</i>
	<i>Tripylina</i> sp.	<i>Panagrolaimus cf. magnivulvatus</i>	<i>Prismatolaimus</i> sp.
	<i>Tylencholaimus mirabilis</i>	<i>Panagrolaimus rigidus</i>	<i>Pseudacrobeles (P.) unguicolis</i>
	<i>Tylencholaimus proximus</i>	<i>Paracephalobus bodenheimeri</i>	<i>Pungentus</i> sp.
	<i>Tylocephalus auriculatus</i>	<i>Pelodera</i> sp.	<i>Tripyla</i> sp.
	<i>Wilsonema ottophorum</i>	<i>Phallaxonchium insolitum</i>	<i>Tylencholaimellus striatus</i>
		<i>Plectus parietinus</i>	<i>Tylencholaimus teres</i>
		<i>Plectus parvus</i>	<i>Tylocephalus auriculatus</i>
		<i>Prismatolaimus</i> sp.	
		<i>Protorhabditis</i> sp.	
		<i>Pseudacrobeles (P.) unguicolis</i>	
		<i>Pungentus</i> sp.	
		<i>Sectonema</i> sp.	
		<i>Stegelletina devimucronata</i>	
		<i>Stegelletina similis</i>	

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		<i>Tripyla</i> sp.	
		<i>Tripylina</i> sp.	
		<i>Tylencholaimus proximus</i>	
		<i>Tylencholaimus teres</i>	
		<i>Tylocephalus auriculatus</i>	
		<i>Wilsonema ottophorum</i>	
Portugal	Traditional 35 taxon/6 samples	Organic 32 taxon/6 samples	High-density 37 taxon/18 samples
	<i>Achromadora</i> sp.	<i>Acrobeles aenigmaticus</i>	<i>Acrobeles complexus</i>
	<i>Acrobeles aenigmaticus</i>	<i>Acrobeles complexus</i>	<i>Acrobeles singulus</i>
	<i>Acrobeles complexus</i>	<i>Acrobeles singulus</i>	<i>Acrobeloides nanus</i>
	<i>Acrobeles singulus</i>	<i>Acrobeloides nanus</i>	<i>Acrobeloides tricornis</i>
	<i>Acrobeloides nanus</i>	<i>Acrobeloides tricornis</i>	<i>Aporcelaimellus obtusicaudatus</i>
	<i>Acrobeloides tricornis</i>	<i>Aporcelaimellus obtusicaudatus</i>	<i>Aporcella</i> sp. 3
	<i>Alaimus</i> sp.	<i>Bursilla vernalis</i>	<i>Aulolaimus cribratus</i>
	<i>Aporcelaimellus hyalinus</i>	<i>Cervidellus vexilliger</i>	<i>Belondira tarjani</i>
	<i>Aporcelaimellus obtusicaudatus</i>	<i>Chiloplacus demani</i>	<i>Bursilla vernalis</i>
	<i>Aporcella</i> sp. 1	<i>Chiloplacus tenuis</i>	<i>Ceratoplectus armatus</i>
	<i>Bursilla vernalis</i>	<i>Chiloplacus trilineatus</i>	<i>Cervidellus vexilliger</i>
	<i>Cephalobus persegnis</i>	<i>Clarkus papillatus</i>	<i>Chiloplacus trilineatus</i>
	<i>Ceratoplectus armatus</i>	<i>Cruznema tripartitum</i>	<i>Cruznema tripartitum</i>
	<i>Cervidellus vexilliger</i>	<i>Diphtherophora</i> sp.	<i>Diphtherophora</i> sp.
	<i>Clarkus papillatus</i>	<i>Discolaimium</i> sp.	<i>Discolaimium</i> sp.
	<i>Diphtherophora</i> sp.	<i>Dorylaimellus egmonti</i>	<i>Dorylaimellus egmonti</i>
	<i>Discolaimium</i> sp.	<i>Dorylaimellus neocapitatus</i>	<i>Drilocephalobus coomansi</i>
	<i>Dorylaimellus egmonti</i>	<i>Drilocephalobus moldavicus</i>	<i>Drilocephalobus moldavicus</i>
	<i>Dorylaimellus parvulus</i>	<i>Ecumenicus monohystera</i>	<i>Ecumenicus monohystera</i>
	<i>Eucephalobus hooperi</i>	<i>Eucephalobus hooperi</i>	<i>Mesorhabditis minuta</i>
	<i>Heterorhabditis</i> sp.	<i>Mesodorylaimus ibericus</i>	<i>Microdorylaimus</i> sp.
	<i>Microdorylaimus</i> sp.	<i>Panagrolaimus rigidus</i>	<i>Mylonchulus sigmaturus</i>
	<i>Monhystrella</i> sp.	<i>Panagrolaimus</i> sp.	<i>Mylonchulus subsimilis</i>
	<i>Mylonchulus sigmaturus</i>	<i>Pelodera</i> sp.	<i>Panagrolaimus rigidus</i>
	<i>Mylonchulus subsimilis</i>	<i>Plectus parietinus</i>	<i>Panagrolaimus</i> sp.
	<i>Oxydirus oxicephalus</i>	<i>Plectus parvus</i>	<i>Paracephalobus bodenheimeri</i>
	<i>Panagrolaimus</i> sp.	<i>Plectus</i> sp.	<i>Paravulvus cf. teres</i>
	<i>Panagrolaimus superbus</i>	<i>Protorhabditis</i> sp.	<i>Pelodera</i> sp.
	<i>Pelodera</i> sp.	<i>Pseudacrobeles (P.) unguicolis</i>	<i>Plectus parietinus</i>
	<i>Plectus parvus</i>	<i>Stegelletina similis</i>	<i>Plectus parvus</i>
	<i>Protorhabditis</i> sp.	<i>Truxonchus</i> sp.	<i>Prismatolaimus</i> sp.
	<i>Pseudacrobeles (P.) unguicolis</i>	<i>Tylocephalus auriculatus</i>	<i>Protorhabditis</i> sp.
	<i>Tripylina</i> sp.		<i>Pseudacrobeles (P.) unguicolis</i>
	<i>Tylencholaimus proximus</i>		<i>Stegelletina similis</i>
	<i>Tylocephalus auriculatus</i>		<i>Tylencholaimellus striatus</i>
			<i>Tylocephalus auriculatus</i>
			<i>Wilsonema ottophorum</i>
Greece	Traditional 28 taxon/3 samples	Organic 64 taxon/18 samples	High-density 13 taxon/1 samples
	<i>Achromadora</i> sp.	<i>Acrobeles complexus</i>	<i>Acrobeles complexus</i>
	<i>Acrobeles complexus</i>	<i>Acrobeles singulus</i>	<i>Acrobeloides nanus</i>
	<i>Acrobeles singulus</i>	<i>Acrobeloides nanus</i>	<i>Aporcelaimellus obtusicaudatus</i>
	<i>Acrobeloides nanus</i>	<i>Acrobeloides tricornis</i>	<i>Bursilla vernalis</i>
	<i>Acrobeloides tricornis</i>	<i>Alaimus</i> sp.	<i>Chiloplacus bisexualis</i>

	<i>Alaimus</i> sp.	<i>Aporcelaimellus obtusicaudatus</i>	<i>Chiloplacus trilineatus</i>
	<i>Anaplectus</i> sp.	<i>Aporcella</i> sp. 1	<i>Drilocephalobus moldavicus</i>
	<i>Aporcelaimellus obtusicaudatus</i>	<i>Aulolaimus cribatus</i>	<i>Eucephalobus mucronatus</i>
	<i>Bursilla</i> cf. <i>franseni</i>	<i>Aulolaimus quercophilus</i>	<i>Microdorylaimus</i> sp.
	<i>Bursilla vernalis</i>	<i>Belondira tarjani</i>	<i>Panagrolaimus</i> sp.
	<i>Cephalobus persegnis</i>	<i>Bunonema</i> sp.	<i>Panagrolaimus superbus</i>
	<i>Ceratoplectus armatus</i>	<i>Bursilla vernalis</i>	<i>Plectus parvus</i>
	<i>Cervidellus</i> cf. <i>hamatus</i>	<i>Cephalobus persegnis</i>	<i>Pseudacrobeles (P.) unguicolis</i>
	<i>Chiloplacus trilineatus</i>	<i>Ceratoplectus armatus</i>	
	<i>Dorylaimellus egmonti</i>	<i>Cervidellus vexilliger</i>	
	<i>Drilocephalobus moldavicus</i>	<i>Chiloplacus bisexualis</i>	
	<i>Ecumenicus monohystera</i>	<i>Chiloplacus minimus</i>	
	<i>Eucephalobus</i> cf. <i>panaxi</i>	<i>Chiloplacus tenuis</i>	
	<i>Eucephalobus mucronatus</i>	<i>Chiloplacus trilineatus</i>	
	<i>Eudorylaimus</i> sp. 3	<i>Clarkus papillatus</i>	
	<i>Heterorhabditis</i> sp.	<i>Crassolabium etterbergense</i>	
	<i>Plectus</i> cf. <i>longicaudatus</i>	<i>Cruzinema tripartitum</i>	
	<i>Plectus parietinus</i>	<i>Diphtherophora</i> sp.	
	<i>Plectus parvus</i>	<i>Discolaimium</i> sp.	
	<i>Pseudacrobeles (P.) unguicolis</i>	<i>Discolaimus</i> sp.	
	<i>Tripyla</i> sp.	<i>Dorylaimellus egmonti</i>	
	<i>Tylocephalus auriculatus</i>	<i>Dorylaimellus grandis</i>	
	<i>Wilsonema ottophorum</i>	<i>Dorylaimellus neocapitatus</i>	
		<i>Dorylaimellus parvulus</i>	
		<i>Drilocephalobus coomansi</i>	
		<i>Drilocephalobus moldavicus</i>	
		<i>Ecumenicus monohystera</i>	
		<i>Eucephalobus hooperi</i>	
		<i>Eudorylaimus</i> sp. 1	
		<i>Eudorylaimus</i> sp. 2	
		<i>Eudorylaimus</i> sp. 4	
		<i>Eudorylaimus</i> sp. 5	
		<i>Heterorhabditis</i> sp.	
		<i>Mesodorylaimus</i> sp.	
		<i>Mesorhabditis minuta</i>	
		<i>Metaxonchium</i> sp.	
		<i>Microdorylaimus</i> sp.	
		<i>Mylonchulus subsimilis</i>	
		<i>Myolaimus</i> sp.	
		<i>Oscheius tipulae</i>	
		<i>Oxydirus oxicephalus</i>	
		<i>Panagrolaimus rigidus</i>	
		<i>Panagrolaimus</i> sp.	
		<i>Paracephalobus bodenheimeri</i>	
		<i>Pelodera</i> sp.	
		<i>Plectus parietinus</i>	
		<i>Plectus parvus</i>	
		<i>Plectus</i> sp.	
		<i>Pristionchus</i> sp.	
		<i>Protorhabditis</i> sp.	

		<i>Pseudacrobeles (P.) unguicolis</i>	
		<i>Pungentus</i> sp.	
		<i>Stegelletina devimucronata</i>	
		<i>Steinernema</i> sp.	
		<i>Tricephalobus</i> sp.	
		<i>Tripyla</i> sp.	
		<i>Tylencholaimellus cf. loofi</i>	
		<i>Tylocephalus auriculatus</i>	
		<i>Wilsonema ottophorum</i>	
Morocco	Traditional 38 taxon/8 samples	Organic 19 taxon/2 samples	High-density 35 taxon/8 samples
	<i>Acrobeles complexus</i>	<i>Acrobeles singulus</i>	<i>Acrobeles complexus</i>
	<i>Acrobeles singulus</i>	<i>Acrobeloides nanus</i>	<i>Acrobeles singulus</i>
	<i>Acrobeloides nanus</i>	<i>Acromoldavicus skrjabini</i>	<i>Acrobeloides nanus</i>
	<i>Acromoldavicus skrjabini</i>	<i>Aporcelaimellus obtusicaudatus</i>	<i>Alaimus</i> sp.
	<i>Aporcelaimellus obtusicaudatus</i>	<i>Belondira tarjani</i>	<i>Aporcelaimellus hyalinus</i>
	<i>Aulolaimus cribatus</i>	<i>Bursilla vernalis</i>	<i>Aporcelaimellus obtusicaudatus</i>
	<i>Aulolaimus quercophilus</i>	<i>Cervidellus vexilliger</i>	<i>Aporcella</i> sp. 3
	<i>Belondira tarjani</i>	<i>Chiloplacus magnus</i>	<i>Aulolaimus cribatus</i>
	<i>Bursilla vernalis</i>	<i>Chiloplacus trilineatus</i>	<i>Bursilla vernalis</i>
	<i>Cephalobus persegnis</i>	<i>Discolaimium</i> sp.	<i>Campydora</i> sp.
	<i>Ceratoplectus armatus</i>	<i>Dorylaimellus egmonti</i>	<i>Cephalobus persegnis</i>
	<i>Cervidellus vexilliger</i>	<i>Dorylaimellus grandis</i>	<i>Cephalobus persegnis</i>
	<i>Chiloplacus minimus</i>	<i>Dorylaimellus parvulus</i>	<i>Ceratoplectus armatus</i>
	<i>Chiloplacus trilineatus</i>	<i>Drilocephalobus coomansi</i>	<i>Cervidellus vexilliger</i>
	<i>Discolaimium</i> sp.	<i>Ecumenicus monohystera</i>	<i>Chiloplacus tenuis</i>
	<i>Discolaimus mariae</i>	<i>Microdorylaimus</i> sp.	<i>Chiloplacus trilineatus</i>
	<i>Discolaimus</i> sp.	<i>Paracephalobus bodenheimeri</i>	<i>Discolaimium</i> sp.
	<i>Dorylaimellus egmonti</i>	<i>Pseudacrobeles (P.) unguicolis</i>	<i>Dorylaimellus</i> sp. 3
	<i>Dorylaimellus grandis</i>	<i>Tylocephalus auriculatus</i>	<i>Drilocephalobus coomansi</i>
	<i>Dorylaimellus parvulus</i>		<i>Ecumenicus monohystera</i>
	<i>Drilocephalobus coomansi</i>		<i>Eudorylaimus</i> sp. 1
	<i>Drilocephalobus moldavicus</i>		<i>Eudorylaimus</i> sp. 3
	<i>Ecumenicus monohystera</i>		<i>Microdorylaimus</i> sp.
	<i>Eudorylaimus</i> sp. 1		<i>Nothacrobeles cf. lunensis</i>
	<i>Eudorylaimus</i> sp. 3		<i>Panagrolaimus cf. magnivulvatus</i>
	<i>Geomonhystera</i> sp.		<i>Panagrolaimus rigidus</i>
	<i>Mesorhabditis minuta</i>		<i>Panagrolaimus</i> sp.
	<i>Microdorylaimus</i> sp.		<i>Paracephalobus bodenheimeri</i>
	<i>Panagrolaimus</i> sp.		<i>Plectus parietinus</i>
	<i>Paracephalobus bodenheimeri</i>		<i>Plectus parvus</i>
	<i>Paraxonchium</i> sp.		<i>Protorhabditis</i> sp.
	<i>Plectus parietinus</i>		<i>Pseudacrobeles (P.) unguicolis</i>
	<i>Plectus parvus</i>		<i>Stegelletina devimucronata</i>
	<i>Protorhabditis</i> sp.		<i>Tylencholaimus teres</i>
	<i>Pseudacrobeles (P.) unguicolis</i>		<i>Tylocephalus auriculatus</i>
	<i>Stegelletina devimucronata</i>		<i>Wilsonema ottophorum</i>
	<i>Tylocephalus auriculatus</i>		
	<i>Wilsonema ottophorum</i>		
Italy	Traditional	Organic	High-density

	9 taxon/15 samples	9 taxon/21 samples	
	<i>Acrobeles</i>	<i>Acrobeles</i>	
	<i>Acrobeloides</i>	<i>Cephalobus</i>	
	<i>Cephalobus</i>	<i>Diplogastridae</i>	
	<i>Dorylaimidae</i>	<i>Dorylaimidae</i>	
	<i>Eucephalobus</i>	<i>Eucephalobus</i>	
	<i>Mononchida</i>	<i>Mononchida</i>	
	<i>Mylonchulus</i>	<i>Mylonchulus</i>	
	<i>Panagrolaimus</i>	<i>Panagrolaimus</i>	
	<i>Rhabditidae</i>	<i>Rhabditidae</i>	

3.2 Plant-parasitic nematodes and nematode biocontrol agents (Task 5.2, IAS-CSIC/CNR)

3.2.1. Plant-parasitic nematodes

3.2.1.1. Diversity and abundance of plant-parasitic nematodes and overall nematode communities in the olive groves studied.

We found different patterns for the alpha diversity indices analyzed between agronomic management systems and countries (**Fig. 9**). While species richness showed similar values (**Fig. 9**), we found differences between agronomic management systems and countries for Shannon index (**Fig. 9**). Notably, we found lower values in olive orchards with a high-density compared to those with organic management systems in most countries. However, the effect of traditional management in olive orchards did not show a similar pattern in all countries in comparison to the other agronomic managements. Moreover, Shannon index was higher in organic groves in Morocco and Spain (**Fig. 9**). High-density groves showed a similar trend of diversity to traditional. Traditional groves in Spain showed the lowest values for Shannon index. This point must be further studied in the future because many of these groves were sampled during an important drought (many fields were under irrigation restriction or rain-feed) and this could affect the nematode diversity for more sensible genera.

Figure 9. Diversity indexes of **plant-parasitic nematode** communities from soil samples. Data referred per 500 cm³ of soil by country and type of agronomic management systems.

The abundance of the overall nematode community and plant-parasitic nematode communities are showed in **Fig. 10**. The countries with the highest density of plant-parasitic nematodes were in Greece, Morocco and Spain, while the lowest were in Italy and Portugal. This higher density of plant-parasitic nematodes was mainly correlated with the higher overall number of the nematode community for Greece and Spain, while for Morocco, this was only found for the traditional olive groves because the other management systems showed contrary results indicating a higher proportion of free-living nematodes with respect to the number of plant-parasitic nematodes.

Figure 10. Abundance of the overall nematode and **plant-parasitic nematode** communities from soil samples. Data referred per 500 cm³ of soil by country and agronomic management systems.

3.2.1.2. Inventory of plant-parasitic nematodes

111 species were found from 32 genera in the soil studied samples in the five countries studied (Spain, Portugal, Morocco, Italy, and Greece) and the three different management systems (Traditional, Organic and High-density). The most diverse genera are the pin nematode genus *Paratylenchus* (17 species), followed by the dagger nematode genus *Xiphinema* (16 species) and the spiral nematode genus *Helicotylenchus* (7 species). **Figure 11** showed the diversity of the genera depending of the number of species found.

	<i>Helicotylenchus digonicus</i>	<i>Ditylenchus</i> sp. ¹	<i>Helicotylenchus digonicus</i>
	<i>Helicotylenchus oleae</i>	<i>Filenchus ditissimus</i>	<i>Helicotylenchus</i> sp2. SO17_4
	<i>Helicotylenchus vulgaris</i>	<i>Filenchus</i> sp.	<i>Helicotylenchus vulgaris</i>
	<i>Ogma</i> sp1.	<i>Filenchus vulgaris</i>	<i>Hexatylyus</i> sp.
	<i>Paratylenchus goodeyi</i>	<i>Geocenamus brevidens</i>	<i>Meloidogyne incognita</i>
	<i>Paratylenchus indalus</i>	<i>Helicotylenchus digonicus</i>	<i>Meloidogyne javanica</i>
	<i>Paratylenchus israelensis</i>	<i>Helicotylenchus oleae</i>	<i>Paratrichodorus paraallius</i>
	<i>Paratylenchus nanus</i>	<i>Helicotylenchus</i> sp1. SO17_1	<i>Paratylenchus salubris</i>
	<i>Paratylenchus sheri</i>	<i>Helicotylenchus vulgaris</i>	<i>Paratylenchus idalimus</i>
	<i>Paratylenchus veruculatus</i>	<i>Heterodera</i> sp.	<i>Paratylenchus pedrami</i>
	<i>Paratylenchus wuae</i>	<i>Longidorus magnus</i>	<i>Paratylenchus veruculatus</i>
	<i>Paurodontella</i> sp.	<i>Longidorus vineacola</i>	<i>Tylenchorhynchus mediterraneus</i>
	<i>Pratylenchus</i> sp. WB	<i>Ogma</i> sp1.	<i>Tylenchus davainei</i>
	<i>Pratylenchus vovlasi</i>	<i>Paratrophurus loofi</i>	<i>Xiphinema luci</i>
	<i>Rotylenchus</i> sp. SO_41_1	<i>Paratylenchus holdemani</i>	<i>Xiphinema nuragicum</i>
	<i>Tylenchorhynchus mediterraneus</i>	<i>Paratylenchus idalimus</i>	<i>Xiphinema sphaerocephalum</i>
	<i>Tylenchus davainei</i>	<i>Paratylenchus israelensis</i>	
	<i>Xiphinema luci</i>	<i>Paratylenchus nanus</i>	
	<i>Xiphinema nuragicum</i>	<i>Paratylenchus sheri</i>	
	<i>Xiphinema sphaerocephalum</i>	<i>Paratylenchus</i> sp. 12	
	<i>Xiphinema turcicum</i>	<i>Paratylenchus</i> sp. 96_holdemani	
		<i>Pratylenchus</i> sp. 1WB_2017	
		<i>Pratylenchus</i> sp. WB	
		<i>Pratylenchus vovlasi</i>	
		<i>Rotylenchus</i> sp. SO_41_1	
		<i>Trophurus</i> sp.	
		<i>Tylenchorhynchus mediterraneus</i>	
		<i>Tylenchus davainei</i>	
		<i>Xiphinema baetica</i>	
		<i>Xiphinema incertum</i>	
		<i>Xiphinema luci</i>	
		<i>Xiphinema nuragicum</i>	
		<i>Xiphinema pachtaicum</i>	
Portugal	Traditional 21 taxon/6 samples	Organic 11 taxon/6 samples	High-density 26 taxon/18 samples
	<i>Aglenchus agricola</i>	<i>Aglenchus agricola</i>	<i>Aorolaimus perscitus</i>
	<i>Aphelenchus avenae</i> ²	<i>Aphelenchus avenae</i> ²	<i>Aphelenchoides</i> sp. ¹
	<i>Bitylenchus maximus</i>	<i>Ditylenchus</i> sp. ¹	<i>Aphelenchus avenae</i> ²
	<i>Boleodorus volutus</i>	<i>Filenchus</i> sp.	<i>Aphelenchus</i> sp. ¹
	<i>Criconemoides informis</i>	<i>Geocenamus brevidens</i>	<i>Bitylenchus hispaniensis</i>
	<i>Filenchus</i> sp.	<i>Helicotylenchus digonicus</i>	<i>Boleodorus volutus</i>
	<i>Geocenamus brevidens</i>	<i>Heterodera carotae</i>	<i>Ditylenchus</i> sp.
	<i>Helicotylenchus vulgaris</i>	<i>Paratylenchus</i> sp. 19	<i>Filenchus</i> sp.
	<i>Paratrichodorus paraallius</i>	<i>Pratylenchus crenatus</i>	<i>Filenchus vulgaris</i>
	<i>Paratylenchus neoprojectus</i>	<i>Tylenchorhynchus mediterraneus</i>	<i>Geocenamus brevidens</i>
	<i>Paratylenchus straeleni</i>	<i>Xiphinema nuragicum</i>	<i>Helicotylenchus digonicus</i>

	<i>Paratylenchus wuae</i>		<i>Meloidogyne incognita</i>
	<i>Pratylenchus crenatus</i>		<i>Neodolichorhynchus</i> sp. 22
	<i>Pratylenchus neglectus</i>		Ogma sp1.
	<i>Pratylenchus</i> sp. WB		<i>Paratylenchus salubris</i>
	<i>Trichodorus giennensis</i>		<i>Paratylenchus holdemani</i>
	<i>Tylenchus elegans</i>		<i>Paratylenchus israelensis</i>
	<i>Xiphinema nuragicum</i>		<i>Paratylenchus pedrami</i>
	<i>Xiphinema pachticum</i>		<i>Paratylenchus sheri</i>
	<i>Xiphinema sphaerocephalum</i>		<i>Pratylenchus crenatus</i>
	<i>Xiphinema</i> sp1 SO_6_7		<i>Pratylenchus</i> sp. WB
			<i>Trophurus</i> sp.
			<i>Tylenchus davainei</i>
			<i>Tylenchus</i> sp.
			<i>Xiphinema luci</i>
			<i>Xiphinema nuragicum</i>
Greece	Traditional 29 taxon/42 samples	Organic 30 taxon/42 samples	High-density 9 taxon/6 samples
	<i>Aglenchus agricola</i>	<i>Aglenchus agricola</i>	<i>Aphelenchoides</i> sp. ¹
	<i>Aphelenchus avenae</i>	<i>Aphelenchus avenae</i>	<i>Aphelenchus</i> sp. ¹
	<i>Aphelenchus</i> sp.	<i>Aphelenchus</i> sp.	<i>Bitylenchus hispaniensis</i>
	<i>Bitylenchus hispaniensis</i>	<i>Bitylenchus hispaniensis</i>	<i>Ditylenchus</i> sp. ¹
	<i>Bitylenchus</i> sp3. SO_40_1	<i>Bitylenchus</i> sp3. SO_40_1	<i>Filenchus</i> sp.
	<i>Coslenchus costatus</i>	<i>Coslenchus costatus</i>	<i>Geocenamus brevidens</i>
	<i>Criconemoides informis</i>	<i>Criconemoides informis</i>	<i>Helicotylenchus digonicus</i>
	<i>Ditylenchus</i> sp. ¹	<i>Criconemoides</i> sp2. SO23	<i>Pratylenchus</i> sp. 1WB_2017
	<i>Filenchus</i> sp.	<i>Ditylenchus dipsaci</i>	<i>Pratylenchus vovlasi</i>
	<i>Geocenamus brevidens</i>	<i>Ditylenchus</i> sp. ¹	
	<i>Helicotylenchus digonicus</i>	<i>Filenchus</i> sp.	
	<i>Helicotylenchus oleae</i>	<i>Filenchus vulgaris</i>	
	<i>Heterodera carotae</i>	<i>Geocenamus brevidens</i>	
	Ogma sp1.	<i>Helicotylenchus digonicus</i>	
	Ogma sp2. SO_41_2	<i>Helicotylenchus vulgaris</i>	
	<i>Paratylenchus idalimus</i>	<i>Meloidogyne hispanica</i>	
	<i>Paratylenchus neoprojectus</i>	<i>Meloidogyne javanica</i>	
	<i>Paratylenchus pedrami</i>	<i>Paratylenchus neoprojectus</i>	
	<i>Paratylenchus</i> sp. 5 SAS	<i>Paratylenchus projectus</i>	
	<i>Paratylenchus veruculatus</i>	<i>Paratylenchus veruculatus</i>	
	<i>Pratylenchus neglectus</i>	<i>Pratylenchus neglectus</i>	
	<i>Pratylenchus</i> sp. WB	<i>Pratylenchus</i> sp. 1WB_2017	
	<i>Pratylenchus vovlasi</i>	<i>Pratylenchus</i> sp. WB	
	<i>Psilenchus hilarulus</i>	<i>Pratylenchus thornei</i>	
	<i>Rotylenchulus borealis</i>	<i>Pratylenchus vovlasi</i>	
	<i>Rotylenchulus robustus</i>	<i>Rotylenchulus borealis</i>	
	<i>Tylenchorhynchus mediterraneus</i>	<i>Tylenchorhynchus mediterraneus</i>	
	<i>Tylenchus elegans</i>	<i>Tylenchus elegans</i>	
	<i>Xiphinema nuragicum</i>	<i>Xiphinema nuragicum</i>	
		<i>Zygotylenchus guevarai</i>	
Morocco	Traditional	Organic	High-density

	38 taxon/24 samples	19 taxon/6 samples	20 taxon/12 samples
	<i>Amplimerlinius globigerus</i>	<i>Aorolaimus</i> sp1. (SO_33_2)	<i>Aphelenchoides</i> sp. ¹
	<i>Amplimerlinius magnistylus</i>	<i>Aphelenchoides</i> sp. ¹	<i>Aphelenchus avenae</i> ²
	<i>Aorolaimus</i> sp1. (SO_33_2)	<i>Aphelenchus</i> sp. ¹	<i>Aphelenchus</i> sp. ¹
	<i>Aphelenchoides</i> sp. ¹	<i>Bitylenchus</i> sp1. SO_33_5	<i>Bitylenchus</i> sp1. SO_33_5
	<i>Aphelenchus avenae</i> ²	<i>Criconemoides</i> sp3. SO33	<i>Criconema mutabile</i>
	<i>Aphelenchus</i> sp. ¹	<i>Ditylenchus</i> sp. ¹	<i>Ditylenchus</i> sp. ¹
	<i>Bitylenchus</i> sp1. SO_33_5	<i>Filenchus</i> sp.	<i>Filenchus</i> sp.
	<i>Bitylenchus</i> sp2. SO_38_4	<i>Geocenamus brevidens</i>	<i>Geocenamus brevidens</i>
	<i>Boleodorus volutus</i>	<i>Geocenamus nanus</i>	<i>Helicotylenchus digonicus</i>
	<i>Criconema mutabile</i>	<i>Helicotylenchus digonicus</i>	<i>Helicotylenchus oleae</i>
	<i>Criconemoides</i> sp3. SO33	<i>Helicotylenchus oleae</i>	<i>Helicotylenchus vulgaris</i>
	<i>Ditylenchus</i> sp.	<i>Heterodera carotae</i>	<i>Heterodera schachtii</i>
	<i>Filenchus</i> sp.	<i>Heterodera</i> sp.	<i>Paratylenchus veruculatus</i>
	<i>Filenchus vulgaris</i>	<i>Paratylenchus idalimus</i>	<i>Paratylenchus zurgenerus</i>
	<i>Geocenamus brevidens</i>	<i>Pratylenchus</i> sp. WB	<i>Pratylenchus</i> sp. WB
	<i>Geocenamus nanus</i>	<i>Psilenchus hilarulus</i>	<i>Pratylenchus vovlasi</i>
	<i>Helicotylenchus digonicus</i>	<i>Rotylenchulus borealis</i>	<i>Tylenchorhynchus clarus</i>
	<i>Helicotylenchus microlobus</i>	<i>Tylenchus elegans</i>	<i>Tylenchus elegans</i>
	<i>Helicotylenchus oleae</i>	<i>Xiphinema nuragicum</i>	<i>Xiphinema italiae</i>
	<i>Helicotylenchus vulgaris</i>		<i>Xiphinema pachtaicum</i>
	<i>Heterodera carotae</i>		
	<i>Heterodera schachtii</i>		
	<i>Heterodera</i> sp.		
	<i>Meloidogyne arenaria</i>		
	<i>Meloidogyne incognita</i>		
	<i>Paratylenchus veruculatus</i>		
	<i>Paratylenchus zurgenerus</i>		
	<i>Pratylenchus</i> sp. WB		
	<i>Pratylenchus vovlasi</i>		
	<i>Psilenchus hilarulus</i>		
	<i>Tylenchorhynchus clarus</i>		
	<i>Tylenchorhynchus mediterraneus</i>		
	<i>Tylenchus elegans</i>		
	<i>Xiphinema baetica</i>		
	<i>Xiphinema nuragicum</i>		
	<i>Xiphinema pachtaicum</i>		
	<i>Xiphinema</i> sp5 SO_38_6		
	<i>Xiphinema</i> sp6 SO_36_4		
Italy	Traditional 21 taxon/15 samples	Organic 20 taxon/21 samples	High-density
	<i>Aphelenchus avenae</i> ²	<i>Aphelenchoides</i> sp. ¹	
	<i>Aprutides guidetti</i> ²	<i>Aphelenchus avenae</i> ²	
	<i>Bitylenchus hispaniensis</i>	<i>Aprutides guidetti</i> ²	
	<i>Coslenchus costatus</i>	<i>Coslenchus costatus</i>	
	<i>Criconemoides informis</i>	<i>Criconemoides</i> sp. Italy	
	<i>Criconemoides xenoplax</i>	<i>Criconemoides xenoplax</i>	
	<i>Filenchus</i> sp.	<i>Ditylenchus</i> sp. ¹	
	<i>Filenchus vulgaris</i>	<i>Filenchus ditissimus</i>	

	<i>Helicotylenchus digonicus</i>	<i>Filenchus</i> sp.	
	<i>Helicotylenchus</i> sp. Italy	<i>Filenchus vulgaris</i>	
	<i>Helicotylenchus vulgaris</i>	<i>Geocenamus brevidens</i>	
	<i>Longidorus</i> sp. Italy	<i>Helicotylenchus digonicus</i>	
	<i>Paratylenchus</i> sp. Italy	<i>Helicotylenchus</i> sp. Italy	
	<i>Pratylenchus pratensis</i>	<i>Paratylenchus</i> sp. Italy	
	<i>Psilenchus</i> sp. Italy	<i>Pratylenchus pratensis</i>	
	<i>Rotylenchulus macrodoratus</i>	<i>Psilenchus</i> sp. Italy	
	<i>Tylenchorhynchus</i> sp. Italy	<i>Rotylenchulus macrodoratus</i>	
	<i>Tylenchus davainei</i>	<i>Tylenchorhynchus</i> sp. Italy	
	<i>Tylenchus</i> sp.	<i>Tylenchus</i> sp.	
	<i>Xiphinema pachtaicum</i>	<i>Xiphinema pachtaicum</i>	
	<i>Zygotylenchus guevarai</i>		

¹Genera with some species pathogenic to crops the other are fungal-feeders

²Species that could be considered fungal-feeder

3.2.1.3. Plant-parasitic nematode prevalence and abundance in the rhizosphere of olive in the Mediterranean basin

Migratory ectoparasites were the most prevalent and abundant in the olive rhizosphere with the genus *Helicotylenchus* being the most prevalent with more than 80% of the soil samples (**Fig. 12**). *Helicotylenchus* is also the genus with the highest density in 500 cm³ of soil (close to 1000 nematodes in average per 500 cm³ of soil). However, specific species of *Helicotylenchus* in some samples showed a high number of nematodes that could be pathogenic to the crop, such as *Helicotylenchus digonicus* is present in 198 samples from 294 samples and its density ranges from 1 to 4360 nematodes/500 cm³ of soil and it is mainly distributed in Spain and Greece. *Helicotylenchus oleae* and *H. vulgaris* in 28 and 27 samples ranging from 12 to 4510 and from 3 to 3660 nematodes/500 cm³ of soil, while other species, such as *H. microlobus* is found in 8 samples in Morocco (two groves) but at high levels, from 4680 to 8500 nematodes/500 cm³ of soil and in one sample in Spain at low level (96 nematodes/500 cm³ of soil). Other species that needs further analysis in order to clarify its taxonomy as a described species or a new species (Hs17) is only found in two groves in Spain with levels from 104 to 3712 nematodes/500 cm³ of soil. Several species of ectoparasitic spiral nematodes of the genus *Helicotylenchus* have been associated with olive roots (Castillo et al., 2010), some of which were associated with necrosis in olive roots and were considered capable of affecting olive tree growth under particular growing conditions (Inserra et al., 1979). Although olive seems to be well adapted to these parasites, a 78% plant-growth reduction has been found on olive plants inoculated with 1,000 individuals of *H. dihystra* under controlled conditions experiments (Diab and El-Eraki, 1968). Seedlings in field with important growth reduction has been detected with soils infested with 40,8 *H. microlobus*/cm³ of soil in a grove in Caceres in comparison to areas with normal growth (Palomares-Rius, *personal communication*). Probably, this neglected group of nematodes could affect young olive trees in replant situation or adult trees in stress conditions.

Other group of nematodes pathogenic to olive are the root-lesion nematodes (*Pratylenchus* spp.). Major species affecting woody plants worldwide are *P. vulnus* and *P. penetrans* (Castillo et al., 2010). In our soil sampling seven species were found (*P.*

crenatus, *P. neglectus*, *Pratylenchus* sp. 1WB_2017, *Pratylenchus* sp. WB, *P. thornei*, *P. vovlasi*, and *P. pratensis*). *Pratylenchus* sp. 1WB_2017 and *Pratylenchus* sp. WB are species closely related to the species described molecularly in the GenBank (KY828334) and isolated from lentils (*Lens culinaris*) in Italy by Jansen et al. (2017). We have not found neither *P. vulnus* nor *P. penetrans* in our sampling. Some of this species showed high levels in the rhizosphere of olive, such as *Pratylenchus* sp. 1WB_2017 with 1056 nematodes/500 cm³ of soil in a high-density sample in Greece (GR-HD43). *Meloidogyne* species are important parasites that could cause important damage in olive trees and they will be described in a special point in the deliverable. Unfortunately, no root samples were found in Morocco and Italian samples and in this sense, we could not correlate the soil levels with damage to the roots in some cases.

Figure 12. Plant-parasitic nematode genera abundance per 500 cm³ and prevalence in the soil samples studied (6 samples/grove). Nematode are separated by feeding type (Microherbivorous: feeding on hair roots, small damage to plants; Migratory ectoparasites: nematodes live in soil and feed on the first root cell layers; Migratory endoparasite: nematodes live in the root, but they could go to other root through soil; Sedentary endoparasites: nematodes live in the root at exception of the infective stage (usually second-stage juveniles or J2), they are important parasites in agriculture (*Meloidogyne* spp., *Heterodera* spp.); Semiendoparasites: most of their live are

ectoparasites and females live embedded partially in the root cortex (*Rotylenchulus* spp.)).

3.2.1.4. Plant-parasitic nematodes in roots. Diversity and prevalence.

Plant-parasitic nematodes in roots were correlated with the species detected in the soil **Table 6**. The nematodes extracted in association to the olive roots are more likely to be feeding on olive roots, while plant-parasitic nematodes not extracted associated to the olive roots could feed on other plants, such as weeds during specific periods of the year. At exception of migratory (*Pratylenchus* spp.) or sedentary endoparasites (*Meloidogyne* spp.), the rest of plant-parasitic nematodes are associated with the levels of nematodes in soil. The most prevalent genus is *Helicotylenchus*, present in close of the 55% of the root samples, but at low level. *Helicotylenchus* could feed (depending of the species) embedding the anterior part several layers of cells in the root and in this way, they could be extracted if they did not fall with the root attached soil. The nematode genera with the highest levels of nematodes in the roots are *Pratylenchus* and *Meloidogyne*, with 150 nematodes/g and 80 nematodes/g of root in average in the positive samples. The main two species found in roots are *P. crenatus* (6 samples in Spain and Greece) and *Pratylenchus* sp. 1WB_2017 (1 sample in Spain). As referred earlier, *Pratylenchus* sp. 1WB_2017 and *Pratylenchus* sp. WB are species closely related to the species described molecularly in the GenBank (KY828334) and isolated from lentils (*Lens culinaris*) in Italy by Jansen *et al.* (2017).

Figure 13. Plant-parasitic nematode genera abundance per g of root and prevalence in the root samples studied from 3 countries where the roots were available (Spain, Portugal and Greece). Nematode are separated by feeding type (Migratory ectoparasites: nematodes live in soil and feed on the first root cell layers; Migratory endoparasite: nematodes live in the root, but they could go to other root through soil; Sedentary endoparasites: nematodes live in the root at exception of the infective stage (usually second stage juveniles or J2), they are important parasites in agriculture (*Meloidogyne* spp., *Heterodera* spp.); Semiendoparasites: most of their live are ectoparasites and females live embedded partially in the root cortex (*Rotylenchulus* spp.).

3.2.1.5. Root-knot nematodes. Important plant-parasitic nematodes in olive.

Root-knot nematodes (*Meloidogyne* spp.) are important plant-parasitic nematodes that in conducive soil conditions could reduce the plant-growth and productivity of olive oil (Castillo et al., 2010). Damage threshold level for *M. javanica* is quantified from 0.49 to 0.91 nematodes/cm³ of soil (Castillo et al., 2010), while other authors find reductions of stem length of 37.6% and 10.7% with inoculations of 0.1 and 12.8 juveniles/cm³ of soil for *M. javanica* and *M. incognita* (Afshar et al., 2014). Four species were detected in samplings (including soil and/or roots), which are: i) *M. javanica* (most pathogenic in olive); ii) *M. arenaria*, iii) *M. incognita*, and iv) *M. hispanica*. The total prevalence was 15,4% of the groves (8/52 groves) and the most prevalent species were *M. incognita*: 3 in 52 groves (5,7% of the groves and found in Morocco, Portugal and Spain) and *M.*

hispanica: 3 in 52 groves (5,7% of the groves and found in Greece and Portugal); followed by *M. javanica*: 2 in 52 groves (3,9% of the groves and found in Spain and Greece) and *M. arenaria*: 1 in 52 groves (1,9% of the groves and found in Morocco). The highest levels in roots were found for *M. javanica* in Spain (240 eggs/g of root), which is in correspondence of the high pathogenicity of this species in olive. The other species were present at not damaging levels in soil. In former studies, *Meloidogyne* nematode levels and prevalence were also higher for *M. javanica* in olive groves in Spain (Archidona-Yuste et al., 2018) and in Morocco (Hamza et al., 2017b).

3.2.2. Nematode biocontrol agents

3.2.2.1. qPCR biocontrol fungal detection in nematode samples

21, 48, 45 and 15 soil nematode samples from Morocco, Spain, Greece and Portugal (3 samples per field with two technical replicates) from all the groves in these countries were tested for the presence of specific biocontrol agents with different mode of action: i) *Nematode-trapping fungi* (*Arthrobotrys dactyloides*, *A. oligospora*, *Gamsyella gephyropagum*), ii) *Endoparasites* (*Catenaria* sp., *Hirsutella rhossiliensis*), and iii) *Egg-parasitic fungi* (*Purpureocillium lilacinum*). Italian samples were not studied because of the risk of *Xylella fastidiosa* in the soil samples transport. *Gamsyella gephyropagum* and *Catenaria* sp. were not detected infecting nematodes in the studied samples. The most prevalent biocontrol agent in soil nematode groves was *P. lilacinum* (11 groves in Spain, 4 groves in Morocco, 15 groves in Greece and 5 groves in Portugal) (**Table 7**). The endoparasite *H. rhossiliensis* is the second most abundant fungal biocontrol samples with detected presence in Spain (2 groves), Greece (1 grove), and Portugal (1 grove) (**Table 8**). Finally, the nematode-trapping fungi were the less prevalent in the soil nematode samples with *A. dactyloides* (1 grove in Greece and 1 groove in Morocco) (**Table 9**) and *A. oligospora* (2 groves in Greece) (**Table 10**).

High density management reduced the prevalence of the *P. lilacinum*, while traditional and organic management showed similar results, at exception of Portugal, where high density showed the highest presence of this fungi (**Table 7**). *Hirsutella rhossiliensis* was not present in high-density management, while it was present in Traditional and Organic management in Spain and only in organic in Portugal and Greece. *Hirsutella rhossiliensis* was not found in Morocco (**Table 8**). *Arthrobotrys dactyloides* was only found in two traditional groves in Morocco and Greece (**Table 9**) and *A. oligospora* was only found one traditional and one organic grove in Greece (**Table 10**).

Table 7. Positive qPCR results for *Purpureocillium lilacinum*

SPAIN		
Traditional	High-density	Organic
ES-TD1	ES-HD2	ES-ORG4
ES-TD5	ES-HD8	ES-ORG11
ES-TD7	ES-HD22 ES-HD40	ES-ORG12 ES-ORG14
MOROCCO		
Traditional	High-density	Organic
MR-TD26 MR-TD27	MR-HD25	MR-ORG23
GREECE		
Traditional	High-density	Organic
GR-TD30 GR-TD31 GR-TD35 GR-TD36 GR-TD37 GR-TD44 GR-TD46	GR-HD43	GR-ORG32 GR-ORG33 GR-ORG34 GR-ORG38 GR-ORG39 GR-ORG45 GR-ORG47
PORTUGAL		
Traditional	High-density	Organic
PT-TD41	PT-HD51 PT-HD52 PT-HD53	PT-ORG42

Table 8. Positive qPCR results for *Hirsutella rhossiliensis*

SPAIN		
Traditional	High-density	Organic
ES-TD1 ES-TD5		ES-ORG14
MOROCCO		
Traditional	High-density	Organic
GREECE		
Traditional	High-density	Organic
		GR-ORG34
PORTUGAL		
Traditional	High-density	Organic
		PT-ORG42

Table 9. Positive qPCR results for *Arthrobotrys dactyloides*

SPAIN		
Traditional	High-density	Organic
MOROCCO		
Traditional	High-density	Organic
MR-TD24		
GREECE		
Traditional	High-density	Organic
GR-TD31		
PORTUGAL		
Traditional	High-density	Organic

Table 10. Positive qPCR results for *Arthrobotrys oligospora*

SPAIN		
Traditional	High-density	Organic
MOROCCO		
Traditional	High-density	Organic
GREECE		
Traditional	High-density	Organic
GR-TD30		GR-ORG33
PORTUGAL		
Traditional	High-density	Organic

3.2.2.2. Egg-bait bioassay in agar-water

The same samples and groves checked by the presence of specific biocontrol agents in the soil nematodes by qPCR were studied using this bioassay in order to detect fungal species that could parasitize eggs in the soil. Italian soils were not included for *Xylella fastidiosa* risk in soil sample transport. Infected eggs are showed in **Fig. 14**.

Figure 14. *Meloidogyne incognita* eggs infected by nematophagous fungi in the egg-bait bioassay in agar-water.

The majority of olive groves positives showed a low percentage of infected eggs in this bioassay with a similar number of groves in all the management studied (**Fig. 15**). The percentage of infected eggs increased the infection rates in organic and traditional management (**Fig. 15**). This data indicates that some levels of biocontrol (even at low infection level) are present in the groves (below 3% percentage).

Figure 15. Infection rate distribution by nematophagous fungi per grove.

The grove management influenced the percentage of eggs infected depending of the country. Organic and traditional grove management in Greece and Traditional in Portugal showed the highest level of egg biocontrol with close to 7% of infected eggs in the bioassay. Spain showed the lowest level of biocontrol in all the management systems with close to 1% of infected eggs. Surprisingly, organic management in Morocco showed an egg infection rate close to 1%. High-density management in Greece showed infection results close to 3%, while in Morocco and Portugal were close to the 2% and to 1% in Spain (**Fig. 16**).

Figure 16. Mean of infected eggs by nematophagous fungi per grove.

171 fungi isolates were obtained from egg-bait agar-water bioassay from infected eggs. Only different plate and fungi morphology were identified molecularly from the same field using the ITS for a preliminary identification (mainly to genus level) (**Table 11**). A second round with additional marker is in process to identify more accurately to species level in some cases, such as *Trichoderma* spp. The majority of the genera found in the olive groves in Europe following the egg-bait agar-water bioassay with soil were *Fusarium* and *Trichoderma*. Many groves showed more than one genus infecting eggs. However, other isolates were identified as *Dactylonectria* spp., *Penicillium* spp., and *Ectophoma pomi* are difficult to assign as fungal infecting actively nematode eggs and they could also be opportunistic fungi in damaged eggs (**Table 11**).

Surprisingly, the presence of active *P. lilacinum* (egg-infecting nematophagous fungi) in the egg-bait agar-water bioassays were not found, while it was recorded in the qPCR data in the majority of the fields, countries and management. The soil was dried to kept at 4 °C until the bioassay, so this could affect the spore survival of this nematophagous fungi. For this reason, is needed the use to additional bioassay protocols to confirm different

biocontrol agents.

Table 11. Preliminary nematophagous fungi identified in the egg-bait agar-water bioassay based on molecular sequencing of ITS marker by country and grove management. For some genus (*Trichoderma*) a second molecular marker will be included for a more accurate species identification. Number of groves for each combination of country and grove management with biocontrol activity is showed and in brackets the number of groves sampled in this combination country and management.

Greece	Traditional 7 (7)	Organic 7 (7)	High-Density 1 (1)
	<i>Ectophoma pomi</i> <i>Fusarium oxysporum</i> <i>Fusarium</i> sp. <i>Penicillium</i> sp. <i>Trichoderma hamatum</i> <i>Trichoderma harzianum</i> <i>Trichoderma koningiopsis</i> <i>Trichoderma</i> sp. <i>Trichoderma sulphureum</i> <i>Trichoderma virens</i>	<i>Fusarium falciforme/solani</i> <i>Fusarium oxysporum</i> <i>Fusarium</i> sp. <i>Trichoderma gamsii</i> <i>Trichoderma hamatum</i> <i>Trichoderma harzianum</i> <i>Trichoderma</i> sp. <i>Trichoderma velutinum</i> <i>Trichoderma virens</i>	<i>Fusarium oxysporum</i>
Spain	Traditional 4 (5)	Organic 6 (6)	High-Density 5 (5)
	<i>Fusarium redolens</i> <i>Fusarium falciforme/solani</i>	<i>Mortirella alpina</i> <i>Dactylonectria</i> sp. <i>Fusarium solani</i> <i>Fusarium oxysporum</i>	<i>Fusarium falciforme/solani</i> <i>Fusarium redolens</i> <i>Fusarium oxysporum</i> <i>Trichoderma virens</i>
Portugal	Traditional 1 (1)	Organic 1 (1)	High-Density 3 (3)
	<i>Fusarium</i> sp. <i>Trichoderma</i> sp. <i>Trichoderma velutinum</i> <i>Trichoderma virens</i> <i>Trichoderma gamsii</i> <i>Fusarium oxysporum</i> <i>Trichoderma hamatum</i> <i>Aspergillus</i> sp.	<i>Trichoderma spirale</i> <i>Trichoderma</i> sp.	<i>Trichoderma gamsii</i> <i>Trichoderma sulphureum</i> <i>Trichoderma spirale</i> <i>Trichoderma velutinum</i> <i>Trichoderma virens</i> <i>Trichoderma</i> sp. <i>Fusarium oxysporum</i>
Morocco	Traditional 4 (4)	Organic 1 (1)	High-Density 2 (2)
	<i>Fusarium</i> sp. <i>Trichoderma</i> sp. <i>Trichoderma spirale</i> <i>Penicillium</i> sp.	<i>Fusarium oxysporum</i>	<i>Fusarium</i> sp. <i>Fusarium oxysporum</i> <i>Fusarium redolens</i> <i>Fusarium nygamai</i>

<i>Fusarium solani</i> <i>Fusarium oxysporum</i>	<i>Talaromyces</i> sp.
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3.3 Ants (Task 5.3)

Abundance.

Figure 17. Boxplot of relative abundances for management types across different countries. ANOVA statistics are shown at the top. Relative abundance was calculated as the proportion of each species with respect to the total abundance within each country and management combination.

To avoid errors caused by nearby ant nests and uncertainty in total ant counts, relative abundance was calculated as the proportion of each species with respect to the total abundance within each country and management combination. The results (Fig. 17) showed that the ANOVA detected significant overall differences in relative species abundance when country and management were considered. However, the pairwise post hoc tests did not find significant differences between any specific groups. This suggests that the significant ANOVA result reflects general variation among groups rather than clear differences between individual pairs, possibly due to high variability within groups or a limited sample size.

List of species.

Country: Greece

Management: **Conventional**

Aphaenogaster spp., *Aphaenogaster spp.1*, *Campanotus spp.*, *Cataglyphis spp.*, *Crematogaster spp.*, *Lepisiota spp.*, *Messor spp.*, *Messor spp.1*, *Monomorium spp.*, *Pheidole spp.*, *Plagiolepis spp.*, *Tapinoma spp.*, *Tapinoma spp.1*, *Tertamorium spp.*, *Tetramorium spp.*, *Thenothorax spp.2*

Management: **Intensive**

Aphaenogaster spp.1, *Lepisiota spp.*, *Monomorium spp.*, *Pheidole spp.*, *Plagiolepis spp.*, *Tapinoma spp.*, *Tetramorium spp.*

Management: **Organic**

Aphaenogaster spp., *Aphaenogaster spp.1*, *Aphaenogaster spp.2*, *Campanotus spp.*, *Campanotus spp.1*, *Campanotus spp1.*, *Campanotus spp.*, *Cataglyphis spp.*, *Crematogaster spp.*, *Formica ssp.*, *Lepisiota spp.*, *Messor spp.*, *Messor spp1.*, *Monomorium spp.*, *Oxyopomyrmex spp.*, *Pheidole spp.*, *Plagiolepis spp.*, *Tapinoma spp.*, *Tertamorium spp.*, *Tetramorium spp.*, *Thenothorax spp.*, *Thenothorax spp.2*, *Trichomyrmex spp.*

Country: Italy

Management: **Conventional**

Aphaenogaster gibbosa, *Aphaenogaster subterranea*, *Camponotus lateralis*, *Camponotus ligniperda*, *Camponotus nylanderi*, *Crematogaster laestrygon*, *Crematogaster scutellaris*, *Lasius lasioides*, *Messor bouveri*, *Messor structor*, *Monomorium subopacum*, *Pheidole sp*, *Plagiolepis sp*, *Tetramorium semileave*

Management: **Organic**

Aphaenogaster gibbosa, *Aphaenogaster sardoa*, *Aphaenogaster subterranea*, *Camponotus ligniperda*, *Camponotus nylanderi*, *Cataglyphis sp*, *Crematogaster laestrygon*, *Crematogaster scutellaris*, *Messor capitatus*, *Messor minor*, *Messor structor*, *Monomorium subopacum*, *Pheidole sp*, *Plagiolepis sp*, *Tetramorium caespitum-impurum*, *Tetramorium semileave*

Country: Portugal

Management: **Conventional**

Aphaenogaster gibbosa, *Aphaenogaster senilis*, *Bothriomyrmex atlantis*, *Camponotus sylvaticus*, *Cataglyphis hispanica*, *Cataglyphis iberica*, *Cataglyphis velox*, *Crematogaster auberti*, *Crematogaster scutellaris*, *Goniomma hispanicum*, *Messor barbarus*, *Messor capitatus*, *Messor ibericus*, *Myrmecina gramminicola*, *Myrmica aloba*, *Plagiolepis schmitzii*, *Solenopsis sp*, *Tapinoma erraticum*, *Tapinoma nigerrimum*, *Tetramorium forte*

Management: **High density**

Aphaenogaster dulcineae, Aphaenogaster gibbosa, Aphaenogaster iberica, Aphaenogaster senilis, Camponotus aethiops, Camponotus amaerus, Camponotus fallax, Camponotus foreli, Camponotus sylvaticus, Cataglyphis hispanica, Cataglyphis iberica, Cataglyphis velox, Crematogaster auberti, Crematogaster scutellaris, Iberoformica subrufa, Lasius grandis, Messor barbarus, Messor capitatus, Messor ibericus, Myrmica aloba, Pheidole palliduda, Plagiolepis pygmaea, Plagiolepis schmitzii, Proformica nasuta, Tapinoma erraticum, Tapinoma nigerrimum, Tetramorium forte

Management: Organic

Camponotus aethiops, Camponotus pilicornis, Cataglyphis hispanica, Cataglyphis iberica, Cataglyphis velox, Crematogaster auberti, Crematogaster scutellaris, Messor barbarus, Messor capitatus, Messor ibericus, Myrmica aloba, Plagiolepis pygmaea, Tapinoma erraticum, Tapinoma nigerrimum, Tetramorium forte

Country: Spain

Management: Conventional

Aphaenogaster dulcineae, Aphaenogaster gibbosa, Aphaenogaster iberica, Aphaenogaster senilis, Camponotus barbaricus, Camponotus foreli, Camponotus micans, Camponotus piceus, Camponotus pilicornis, Camponotus sylvaticus, Cataglyphis hispanica, Cataglyphis iberica, Cataglyphis rosenhaueri, Cataglyphis velox, Crematogaster auberti, Crematogaster sordidula, Iberoformica subrufa, Lasius grandis, Lasius lasioides, Lasius niger, Messor barbarus, Messor capitatus, Messor ibericus, Monomorium salomonis, Pheidole palliduda, Plagiolepis pygmaea, Plagiolepis schmitzii, Proformica ferreri, Tapinoma erraticum, Tapinoma nigerrimum, Temnothorax recedens, Tetramorium forte, Tetramorium semileave

Management: High density

Aphaenogaster dulcineae, Aphaenogaster gibbosa, Aphaenogaster iberica, Aphaenogaster senilis, Aphaenogaster striativentris, Camponotus aethiops, Camponotus amaerus, Camponotus barbaricus, Camponotus foreli, Camponotus piceus, Cardiocondyla batesii, Cardiocondyla elegans, Cataglyphis rosenhaueri, Cataglyphis velox, Iberoformica subrufa, Lasius grandis, Messor barbarus, Messor bouberti, Messor capitatus, Messor hispanicus, Messor ibericus, Myrmica aloba, Pheidole palliduda, Plagiolepis pygmaea, Plagiolepis schmitzii, Plagiolepis pygmaea, Solenopsis fugax, Tapinoma erraticum, Tetramorium forte, Tetramorium semileave

Management: Organic

Aphaenogaster dulcineae, Aphaenogaster gibbosa, Aphaenogaster iberica, Aphaenogaster senilis, Camponotus amaerus, Camponotus barbaricus, Camponotus cruentatus, Camponotus foreli, Camponotus lateralis, Camponotus micans, Camponotus micas, Camponotus piceus, Camponotus pilicornis, Camponotus sylvaticus, Cardiocondyla batesii, Cataglyphis rosenhaueri, Cataglyphis velox, Crematogaster auberti, Crematogaster scutellaris, Crematogaster sordidula, Iberoformica subrufa, Lasius grandis, Messor barbarus, Messor capitatus, Messor ibericus, Myrmica aloba, Pheidole palliduda, Plagiolepis pygmaea, Plagiolepis schmitzii, Tapinoma erraticum, Technomyrmex, Tetramorium forte, Tetramorium semileave

Biodiversity indexes.

To compare ant alpha diversity among different countries, management types, and microsites, Hill numbers were calculated: $q = 0$, which represents species richness; $q = 1$, which reflects the diversity of common species and corresponds to the exponential of Shannon entropy; and $q = 2$, which emphasizes dominant species and corresponds to the inverse of Simpson’s index.

Figure 18. Comparative boxplots between countries for the different Hill numbers. ANOVA significance is shown at the top. $q = 0$, which represents species richness; $q = 1$, which reflects the diversity of common species and corresponds to the exponential of Shannon entropy; and $q = 2$, which emphasizes dominant species and corresponds to the inverse of Simpson’s index.

In Figure 18, no significant differences were found in $q1$ or $q2$ between countries, although there were differences in total species richness ($q0$), with Portugal showing a higher number of species than Greece, which has a lower total number of species. This indicates that, despite Portugal having more species overall, the relative diversity and evenness of species ($q1$ and $q2$) do not differ significantly between the countries.

Figure 19. Comparative boxplots between managements for the different Hill numbers. ANOVA significance is shown at the top. $q = 0$, which represents species richness; $q = 1$, which reflects the diversity of common species and corresponds to the exponential of Shannon entropy; and $q = 2$, which emphasizes dominant species and corresponds to the inverse of Simpson’s index.

At the management level (Fig.19), no significant differences were found among management types due to the high variability within each category. However, some trends were observed. Intensified farms tended to show higher $q1$ and lower $q2$ values, indicating communities with a greater diversity of common species but strongly dominated by one or a few very abundant species. In contrast, organic farms showed lower $q1$ and higher $q2$ values, suggesting communities with fewer common species but a more even distribution of abundances among the dominant species. In all cases, these patterns represent trends in median values only, as no statistically significant differences were detected among

management types.

Figure 20. Comparative boxplots between managements and countries for Jaccard index. ANOVA significance is shown at the top.

To assess ant beta diversity, the Jaccard dissimilarity index was used. In the figure 20, ANOVA showed significant differences between countries, but not among management types, likely due to the variability that country introduces within each management. Spanish and Greek farms exhibited higher Jaccard values, indicating greater species turnover between sites, while Italian orchards showed lower values, reflecting more similar communities. At the management level, although not significant, organic farms showed the lowest Jaccard values, suggesting more homogeneous communities across sites, which is consistent with the low q1 and high q2 values observed, indicating a more even distribution of abundances within each orchard.

Due to the low number of individuals captured in Morocco and the difficulty of achieving accurate identification, these samples were excluded from the general analysis. For completeness, a total of 159 ants were collected and identified to the subfamily level, corresponding to Dolichoderinae and Formicinae. In the future, the samples will be sent to the UJA laboratory for identification at the species level.

4. Conclusions

This report shows a picture of the diversity and abundance of soil nematodes including their biocontrol agents and the ants. This is an initial work, as many species from nematodes (free-living and plant-plant parasitic nematodes) are under study and with the possibility of being a new species description or species for first time detected in some countries. This task requires an important amount of time and expertise to be completed (in some cases, even resampling) because of the morphological diagnosis and characterization is mainly based on adult specimens (sometimes not abundant).

The project found a general diversity of 101 species of free-living nematodes (not all samples analyzed yet) and 111 species from 32 genera in plant-parasitic nematodes (all samples analyzed). For free-living nematodes, the richest nematode order was Rhabditida, with 42 species, while the most diverse genera for plant-parasitic nematodes are *Paratylenchus* (17 species), followed by *Xiphinema* (16 species) and *Helicotylenchus* (7 species). Generally, the diversity of free-living nematodes is bigger than plant-parasitic nematodes as in free-living are including many trophic groups. There is not a clear trend in nematode abundance for olive field management within each country, and in the comparison by country we found that the lowest abundance is for Italy, followed by Portugal. Spain, Morocco and Greece showed similar abundances. However, plant-parasitic nematode levels are similar between the three different management systems for Greece, Italy and Spain, while they increase for traditional management in Morocco and decrease in Portugal (only 1 grove in traditional and organic management system). For free-living nematodes (the work for free-living nematodes is still in process), Spain was the country with more samples analyzed, and the nematode number was higher in the organic management, for the other management system and countries is difficult to find a clear pattern without the analysis of all samples. From the point of view of biodiversity, the organic management showed the higher biodiversity for free-living and plant-parasitic nematodes. This trend has been also detected in former studies (Palomares-Rius et al., 2015). This trend is also observed in Morocco and in Greece. High-density management showed lower diversity using the Shannon index in Greece and Portugal. Plant-parasitic nematodes are strictly feeding on plants and conditions affecting plant diversity and growth are usually affecting their diversity and abundance.

This project found important plant-parasitic nematodes affecting the studied groves, such as root-knot nematodes (*Meloidogyne* spp.) with a diversity of 4 species (*M. hispanica*, *M. javanica*, *M. arenaria* and *M. incognita*) with a prevalence of 15,4% of the groves (8/52 groves). The most pathogenic and with the bigger reproduction factor was *M. javanica*, also shown in former studies (Archidona-Yuste et al., 2018). This species could cause important damage to olive in good conditions, such as high-density fields. We could not find any relationship of this sense in this project, but wide sampling schemes with a higher number of groves showed that olive orchards under super-intensive regimes are more conducive to the multiplication of root-lesion nematodes (*Pratylenchus* spp.) while the presence of irrigated intercrops enhances the multiplication of *Meloidogyne* spp. (Guesmi-Mzoughi et al., 2022). Other interesting group, are the neglected spiral nematodes (*Helicotylenchus* spp.). Some species are widely present in specific countries, such as *H.*

digonicus, mainly distributed in Spain and Greece. Other species showed high levels that could affect the olive productivity, such as, *H. microlobus* that is found in only 8 samples in Morocco (two groves) but at high levels, from 4.680 to 8500 nematodes/500 cm³ of soil and in one sample in Spain at low level (96 nematodes/500 cm³ of soil). Many fields have moderate-high levels of this genus of nematodes and in stress conditions or plantlets could have an effect on growth and productivity.

Only one biocontrol agent affecting nematodes is broadly distributed in olive fields (*P. lilacinum*) from a total of 6 nematophagous fungi studied by qPCR in the nematode soil community: nematode-trapping (*Arthrobotrys dactyloides*, *A. oligospora* and *Gamsyella gephyropagum*), endoparasitic (*Catenaria* sp. and *Hirsutella rhossiliensis*) and eggs-parasitic fungi (*Purpureocillium lilacinum*). The endoparasite *H. rhossiliensis* is the second most abundant fungal biocontrol agent in samples with a detected presence in Spain (2 groves), Greece (1 grove), and Portugal (1 grove). Finally, the nematode-trapping fungi were the less prevalent in the soil nematode samples with *A. dactyloides* (1 grove in Greece and 1 groove in Morocco) and *A. oligospora* (2 groves in Greece). High density management reduced the prevalence of the *P. lilacinum*, while traditional and organic management showed similar results, at exception of Portugal, where high-density management showed the highest presence of this fungus. These results are similar to Campos-Herrera et al. (2022) in a more restricted sampling in Spain. A basal suppressiveness to the *M. incognita* bait in agar-water bioassay showed that there is some biocontrol activity, even at lower level (<3% infected eggs) in all the management system studied, but this biocontrol activity increased with the traditional management and the highest biocontrol activity were found in organic management. This increase in the biocontrol general activity against eggs could be related to a higher presence of soil propagules of the fungi or a higher pathogenicity of the isolated fungi. The biodiversity of these biocontrol agents is mainly in the genera *Fusarium* and *Trichoderma*. The highest biocontrol activity is found in traditional and organic groves in Greece and one organic grove in Portugal.

Regarding ants, our results indicate that country exerts a stronger influence on both alpha and beta diversity than management practices. Portuguese sites showed higher total species richness, while Spanish and Greek sites exhibited greater species turnover, and Italian sites had more homogeneous communities. At the management level, trends suggest that intensified farms tend to host communities with more abundant common species but dominated by few taxa, whereas organic farms support more evenly distributed communities across sites. Overall, these patterns highlight that ant assemblages respond subtly to management intensity, but broader geographic and environmental factors play a more decisive role in shaping community structure and species composition.

In conclusion, management practices may influence the structure and distribution of ant assemblages in olive groves, potentially affecting their contribution to important ecosystem functions. However, for nematode (free-living and plant-parasitic) abundance and biodiversity the field management influence seems more dependent to the country studied. Maybe, other practices that needs to be analyzed in the future in more detail could give a better cue to biodiversity and distribution pattern and their relation with some nematode genera (or species), such as irrigation, soil parameters and climate, as it has been demonstrated in other studies (Palomares-Rius et al., 2015; Guesmi-Mzoughi et al., 2022; Laasli et al., 2023). Organic and traditional practices seem also related to a higher level of biocontrol activity against nematodes. However, a low biocontrol presence is widely present in many countries and conditions, so there is still room for a better biocontrol soil activity by stimulating specific practices more respectful to microbial activity in the soil (such

as, increasing organic matter or reduced tilling).

5. References

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